

National Ribat University
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Cooperation Strategies for Competitors in the
Telecommunication Networks Operation Market

A Thesis Submitted for the PhD Degree in Strategic Studies

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يقول الله تعالى

" فَتَعَالَى اللَّهُ الْمَلِكُ الْحَقُّ ۗ وَلَا تَعْجَلْ بِالْقُرْآنِ مِنْ قَبْلِ أَنْ
يُنْزَلَ إِلَيْكَ وَحْيُهُ ۗ وَقُلْ رَبِّ زِدْنِي عِلْمًا "

سورة طه الآية 114

Dedication

To

My mother

The sole of my father who used to encourage my post graduate studies.

*The sole of my beloved sister **Sumaya**.*

*My Little family: my Life-long companion "**Rania**" and my kids **Abdelmageed** and **Jood**.*

My Sisters

My family members and friends.

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Abstract

Increasing competition, along with investments in ever-changing technology, has been pushing telecom operators towards new ways of maintaining margins. Considering that building and operating telecommunication infrastructure is a significant cost for operators, it is the ideal way to find quick reduction in cost. The estimated Capex and Opex savings resulting from cooperation in building infrastructure can be used in introducing new services and for lowering prices for customers.

The aim of this research is to study effect of adopting cooperation strategies in building telecom infrastructure, the results of the study came out from different field work types.

A site survey has been done to measure the level of implementing cooperation strategies, an interview with telecom experts and decision makers to study the reasons that drive cooperation, the barriers that limit it and how decisions regarding cooperation are done. A model of a 4G network had been done to study the effect of cooperation on capex.

The researcher found the cooperation is very low, only in 3% of the sites and in 11.8% of fiber roots.

The main results were that cooperation will save Capex with minimum 20 % and Opex with minimum 30%, will reduce the enviromental hazards with 50%, while in 4G network the saving in Capex is between 30 and 52%. The main reason that operators do not cooperate is their low willingness to cooperate with competitors.

المستخلص

زيادة المنافسة، جنباً إلى جنب مع الاستثمارات في التقنيات المتغيرة باستمرار ، دعا مشغلي شبكات الاتصالات يسعون للبحث عن طرق جديدة للحفاظ على الهوامش التي تحقق الربحية.

وبالنظر إلى أن إنشاء البنية التحتية وتشغيلها يعتبر ذو تكلفة كبيرة للمشغلين، تعتبر البنية التحتية هي المنطقة المثلى لإيجاد الحلول السريعة لخفض التكلفة . التوفير في النفقات الرأسمالية والتشغيلية الناتجة عن التعاون في بناء البنية التحتية يمكن استخدامها في إدخال خدمات جديدة وتخفيض الأسعار للعملاء.

الهدف من هذا البحث دراسة الآثار الناتجة عن اعتماد استراتيجيات التعاون في بناء البنية التحتية للاتصالات، وقد استخلصت نتائج الدراسة من عدة أنواع من العمل الميدان شملت مسحا ميدانية, مقابلات مع متخصصين ونموذج لشبكة من الجيل الرابع.

لقد تم إنجاز مسح ميداني لقياس مستوى تنفيذ استراتيجيات التعاون بالاضافة لمقابلات مع خبراء في مجال الاتصالات وصناع القرار لدراسة الأسباب التي تدفع بالتعاون والموانع التي تحد من تطبيق استراتيجيات التعاون وكيفية اتخاذ القرارات فيما يتعلق بالتعاون. كما تم تصميم نموذج لشبكة من الجيل الرابع لدراسة تأثير التعاون على الإنفاق الرأسمالي.

ووجد الباحث التعاون منخفض جداً في حدود 3% فقط كحد أعلى في المواقع الخاصة بشبكات الهاتف السيار و 11.8% في مسارات الألياف الضوئية.

وكانت أهم نتائج هذا البحث أن تطبيق استراتيجيات التعاون سيوفر النفقات الرأسمالية بحد أدنى 20% والنفقات التشغيلية بحد أدنى 30%، وتقليل المخاطر البيئية بنسبة 50%، بينما سيكون التوفير في النفقات الرأسمالية لشبكة الجيل الرابع ما بين 30 و 52%، بينما اتضح ان السبب الرئيسي لعد تطبيق استراتيجيات التعاون هو الرغبة المنخفضة للتعاون مع المنافسين.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Section One: Preface

The modern economy puts in front of firms the challenges, which force them to look for new development strategies adequate to the conditions of the global economy based on the continuous changes in the environment, uncertainty of market position, intensified competition, saturation of traditional markets, affaced boundaries between sectors and the demand for continued innovation⁽¹⁾.

These impacts can be particularly visible in the global telecommunication sector, and in consequence, in its counterpart in Sudan.

This sector handles the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in all areas of the economy so as to supply the clients with new products and services, allowing for electronic registration, processing, transmission, reproducing or display of information. More and more frequently, the ICT sector develops very intensely, starts to go beyond the boundaries of other sectors, the Internet and media convergence occurs, and the activity of enterprises belonging to them combine not only the information, communication, entertainment, but also the media, finance or logistics⁽²⁾

This is a result of changes in the global economy, which take place in the technological, economic, social and market environment. The evolution of the sector, led the telecommunication operators to be in a strong competition, which lead to larger investments in building telecommunication networks to provide services for customers in Sudan market, such telecom networks besides the high capital investment needs a long time to cover a large space and geographically diverse nature of a country like Sudan.

¹ Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development., *The Economic Impact of ICT: Measurement, Evidence and Implications*. (France: OECD, 2004), p. 21.

² GOLONKA, M. Konwergencja, konsolidacja, koopetycja - jak zmienia, Consolidation, Coopetition - How the Industry of Information and Communication Technologies Changes (ICT). *Przegląd Organizacji*, 2012, No 3, p. 33-36

Each telecommunication operator started to build networks without coordination with other operators, this led to build several independent networks even in the rural areas and highways where the need for telecommunication services is less and normally not attractive for investors.

Cooperation between competing firms has become an important subject for research. The purpose of this thesis is to get a better understanding of various types of cooperation strategies between competitors and the prospective improvements if it has been applied in the telecommunication sector in Sudan.

Problem Indication

As strategic factors affecting a firm's market position, cooperation and competition have historically been approached independently by researchers. However, pursuing both strategies simultaneously has been the focus of a number of studies (Afuah, 2000; Bengtsson and Kock, 2000; Garcia and Velasco, 2002; Gnyawali and Madhavan, 2001; Luo, 2005).(1)

Also numerous practical examples of cooperation between competitors are available. For example; Fuji and Kodak were intense rivals in the photo paper industry but they were also partners in Research & Development (R&D) projects and the New United Motor Manufacturing Inc partnership between General Motors and Toyota (2).

Despite the various theoretical and practical examples of cooperation between competitors, only recently a stream of research emerged that integrates the contradicting concepts of cooperation and competition with the same firms, which is labeled as *coopetition*.

This research will study whether cooperation can enhance firms competitive position in the market, and for regulation bodies such as telecommunication

1 Michael H. Morris, Akin Koçak and Alper Özer, 'Coopetition as a Small Business Strategy', Journal of Small Business Strategy, 2007, p. 2.

2 Gnyawali, D. R. and Madhavan, R, "Cooperative Networks and Competitive Dynamics: A Structural Embeddedness Perspective", Academy of Management Review, 2001, p 26.

regulators it is valuable to know what the effects of cooperation could be on competition in a market so that they can enforce policies that stimulate cooperation.

Problem Statement

Derived from the problem indication above, the following problem statement is formulated: *Does cooperation strategies create value and what effect does they have on competition in telecommunication sector?*

Research Questions

- 1- What is the effect of cooperation strategies on the market value of the partnering firms?
- 2- What is the effect of cooperation strategies on the Capital expenditure of firms (CAPEX)?
- 3- What is the effect of cooperation strategies on the Operation expenditure of firms (OPEX)?
- 4-What is the effect of cooperation strategies on saving the country's foreign exchange reserves?
- 5- What is the effect of cooperation strategies on saving time during network deployment?
- 6- Why telecom operators in Sudan do not apply cooperation strategies?
- 7- What is the effect of cooperation strategies on environment?

Research Methodology

This thesis will study Sudan's market of telecommunications for the effect of cooperation strategies on market value. In the telecommunications it is very likely that all telecommunications operators compete with each other with different competitive intensity.

In order to research the effect of cooperation strategies on the market value of firms and on competitiveness in a market this study will mainly focus on the cooperative aspects of competition.

The national strategy of Sudan had been studied, also National Telecommunications Corporation (NTC) policies and current strategies, network structures and the degree of cooperation between operators had been studied based on the data collected from the telecom operators and NTC.

A separate data had been collected from site surveys to investigate whether the operators are showing any degree of implementing cooperation strategies or not, this data had been collected from visiting the Base Stations of the various telecom operator in national highway from Khartoum to Port Sudan approximately 800 km and the base stations inside Atbara town.

Interviews with the planning directors and top management of the various telecom operators, the regulator and university professors had been held to discuss the effect of cooperation strategies and to answer the research questions.

A fourth generation mobile network had been designed with help of a telecom equipment vendor and all the levels of cooperation had been tested and the effects of cooperation on each operator had been measured.

Limitations of the Study

This research faces some limitations which might influence the validity and reliability of the results of the study.

- The major limitation is that the concept of cooperation is relatively new in Sudan and it is difficult to find enough cases to study.
- Another limitation is that there were only 40 interviewees in total. Because of the low number of the interviewees the researcher may not reach saturation in the interview results, although some authors said 12 interviewees are enough like Guest et al.(2006)⁽¹⁾ , others argue that it depends on the research type , samples must be large enough to assure that most or all of the perceptions that might be important are covered, but at

¹ GUEST, G., BUNCE, A. & JOHNSON, L. (2006) How Many Interviews Are Enough? An experiment with data saturation and variability. *Field Methods*, 18, 59-82.

the same time if the sample is too large data becomes repetitive. If a researcher remains faithful to the principles of qualitative research, sample size in the majority of qualitative studies should generally follow the concept of saturation , when the collection of new data does not show any further light on the issue under investigation ⁽¹⁾. Without reaching saturation we cannot know if the interview results are dependent on the number of the interviews.

Practical reasons such as low number of experts in the field with busy schedules or being on holidays, and the need to complete this study within a specific time period may justify the existence of this limitation.

- Other limitations are lack of previous studies even in Europe and the lack of belief in researches by telecom operators.

Structure of the Thesis

In the next chapter the theoretical matters regarding strategy in general and cooperation strategies are reviewed so as to get a better understanding of the concept.

In chapter three, the telecom networks, their components and cooperation levels in telecommunications infrastructure have been discussed. Also the telecom network situation in Sudan has been explained.

Explanations of the research methodology and the details of field work is laid in Chapter four.

Chapter five deals with the research results and analysis.

Chapter six discusses the results of the analysis, gave answers to the research questions and suggest some recommendations.

¹ Baker, S. & Edwards, R. (2012). How many qualitative interviews is enough? Expert voices and early career reflections on sampling and cases in qualitative research. National Centre for Research Methods discussion paper <http://eprints.ncrm.ac.uk/2273/accessed> 20/5/2016

Section Two: Previous studies

In this section the researcher discusses some researches in the area of cooperation strategies and Telecommunications infrastructure sharing done previously by researchers from different countries; the researcher did not find any such study in Sudan.

Study One

A Master Thesis in International Marketing titled “*Companies’ Reactions to Rival’s Actions in the Fast Moving Consumer Goods, Examples of companies in the cosmetics goods industry*” in 2012 from School of Sustainable Development of Society and Technology, Mälardalens Högskolan University, Sweden by Jolita Kilinskaite.

The purpose of this thesis was to describe and analyze how companies react to rival’s actions. It had a unique research question “ *How companies in the Fast Moving Consumer Goods industry react to rival’s actions* ”

This master thesis concentrates on three common reaction strategies in marketing, which are defined as differentiation, imitation, and coopetition and describes possible rival’s actions, and the root causes of certain reaction strategies. Based on the literature, interviews were conducted with the marketing managers from four different companies in the cosmetics goods industry, in order to prove whether the interviewed managers support the defined reaction strategies. The result was a support for the differentiation and imitation strategies. However, coopetition was only used by one of the companies and is therefore seen as a less important strategy, at least in the marketing departments of the interviewed companies.

Study Two

A Master Thesis in Management titled “*Resource Sharing in Mobile Service Market: Investigating the final decisions of the network operators*” in November 2010 from the Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management, Delft University of Technology, Netherlands by Ioanna Chatzicharistou.

The purpose was to explore how infrastructure sharing can improve the financial situation of the network operators by considering drivers, barriers and trade-offs.

The research questions were:

1. What is infrastructure sharing?
2. What does the resource based view imply for infrastructure sharing?
3. Which are the most important infrastructure sharing drivers, barriers and trade-offs for the network operators and the new entrants?
4. How do the trade-offs affect the choice of infrastructure sharing category?

Depending on the sharing arrangement between the actors involved different levels of savings can be acquired. For example, by applying RAN sharing network operators can enjoy savings of (10-20%) in capital and savings of (20-40%) in operational expenses over a five-year period.

Study Three

A Master Thesis in Management titled “*How an MNC (Multi National Company) can enter Pakistan Telecom mobile market*” in 2009 from the Department of Management, Politics and Philosophy, Copenhagen Business School, Denmark by Nabeel Ahmad.

The Purpose of the study was to discover the appropriate modes of entry strategy for an MNC to successfully enter and establish operations in targeted telecommunication sector of Pakistan.

The study had the following research questions:

1. What are the most prominent theoretical frameworks describing strategies and theories on entry mode in developing economies?
2. How competitive is telecom market in terms of industry, customers and competitors?
3. How MNC can establish operations in target market (telecom) in Pakistan

The main results of the study stated that “The new entrant company during first phase of expansion can follow service based strategy by engaging itself into a joint venture or can start using former entrance competitor’s infrastructure.

Study Four

A Master Thesis in Applied Mathematics titled “*Differentiation Strategies for Operators sharing Universal Mobile Telecommunication Systems (UMTS) Networks*” in 2005 from the Department of Numerical Analysis and Computer Science, Royal Institute of Technology Stockholm, Sweden by Navid Rostam Khesal

The purpose of the research was to study possible differentiation strategies for operators that share UMTS networks. The research questions were:

1. What competition areas exist in individual networks?
2. How do shared networks affect competition in these areas?
3. Are there any competition areas that shared networks do not affect?

The main result of the study stated that the operators should:

- 1- Invest and compete only in services, the main objective should be to offer attractive services.
- 2- Set reasonable prices on the services.

Study Five

A Doctoral thesis in business Management titled “*The balancing act: Cooperating with competitors*” in 2012 from the Faculty of Social Sciences, UMEA School of Business and Economics (USBE), UMEA University, Sweden by Johansson Marlene.

The purpose of the study was to investigate how co-opetition enables Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) to create entrepreneurial opportunities in fast-paced industries.

The research questions were:

- 1- How do firms balance interaction, roles and expectation in co-opetition?

2- How do firms balance power and dependency through portfolios of relationship in coopetition?

3- How do firms balance temporalities in coopetition?

The researcher found that the ability to build legitimacy, to enhance agility and to create role flexibility plays an important role in balancing and navigating among different coooperative relationships, thereby creating and sustaining opportunities.

Study Six

A Master's thesis in Business Administration titled "*Telecom Infrastructure Sharing as a Strategy for Cost Optimization and Revenue Generation: A Case Study of MTN Nigeria/Zain Nigeria Collocation*" in 2009 from the Blekinge Institute of Technology, School of Management, Sweeden by Emeka Onuzuruike.

The main research focus was to examine the current telecom infrastructure model used in Nigeria in order to investigate its strengths and weaknesses from a cost perspective, the research had the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Network infrastructure sharing results in a significant reduction in cost of network infrastructure rollout and capacity expansions for telecoms operators in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: Network infrastructure sharing results in improved efficiency in the utilization of telecoms infrastructure for telecom operators in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3: Network infrastructure sharing leads to a significant reduction in the operational expenditures (OPEX) dissipated for telecoms operators in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 4: Network infrastructure sharing does not lead to degraded quality of service and customer usage experience for telecoms operators in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 5: Network infrastructure sharing will enable telecoms operators in Nigeria achieve and sustain competitive advantage through wider coverage and capacity at less costs.

Hypothesis 6: Network infrastructure sharing would lead to improved service delivery by telecoms providers in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 7: Network infrastructure sharing would positively impact (improve) new product development and service innovation for telecom providers in Nigeria.

The main results were:

1. Operators can obtain 30-40% savings on both CAPEX and OPEX spending by sharing telecommunications infrastructure.
2. operators are able to achieve better competitive advantage through wider coverage in faster and cheaper ways by adopting infrastructure sharing in their business strategies.
3. Infrastructure sharing in telecoms is also seen as a catalyst for better product/service innovations and new product development depending on the company's marketing or sales strategy.

Study Seven

A Master's thesis in Business Administration (International Marketing) titled "*A Study of Bangladesh Telecom Market*" in 2008 from the School of Sustainable Development of Society and Technology Malardalen University, Vasteras, Sweden by Rana Alamgir & Nitin Anand.

The thesis purpose was to investigate Bangladesh telecom market in order to find out the potentiality of the market which could be considered by the company *TeliaSonera* to think about starting a business there and also to determine a suitable entry strategy by the company depending on the factors that have been investigated. The thesis has a unique hypothesis "It is possible for an international

telecom company to enter into Bangladesh telecom market easily if it chooses the appropriate entry strategy”.

After investigating the factors of Bangladesh telecom market, the researchers concluded that it will be a good idea for Teliasonera to expand their business in Bangladesh as both the industry and the country has a lot of potential to offer. An entry strategy (Joint Venture) which is considered to be one of the most important cooperative strategies has been suggested.

Study Eight

A Master’s thesis in Business Administration titled “*The effect of cooperation on the market value of firms: Do cooperative agreements between competitors lead to an increase in market competition?*” in February, 2011 from the School of Economics and Management, Tilburg University, Netherlands by Robin de Baar.

The purpose of the study was to study why do firms prefer cooperation with market rivals instead of cooperating with firms from other markets or industries?

The study had the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: The announcement of a cooperative agreement between competitors leads to positive abnormal returns and therefore has a positive impact on the market value of the participants.

Hypothesis 2: Non-partnering firms will experience negative abnormal returns when competitors from the market form a partnership, indicating an increase in competitive intensity in the market.

Hypothesis 3: The abnormal returns after the announcement of joint manufacturing agreements between competitors are significantly lower than abnormal returns of R&D agreements.

Hypothesis 4: Announcements of cooperative agreements between competitors that involve a high level of cooperation lead to significant higher abnormal returns than cooperative agreements that involve a low level of cooperation.

Hypothesis 5: The abnormal returns of the cooperative network are significantly higher than the abnormal returns of the rivals that are not in the cooperative network.

The main results of research were:

1- It was found that firms prefer to cooperate with competitors to exploit opportunities in their markets that require additional resources to those resources the firm owns.

2- when competitors announced a partnership with each other, this would have a positive impact on their market value since the exploitation of a market opportunity should enhance the competitive position of the firms.

Study Nine

A Master thesis in Strategic Business Analyses titled “*Cooperation among competitors, Analysing sharing scenarios for mobile network operators*” in June 2011 from the Leiden university, Mathematical Institute, Netherlands by Den Haag.

The study aimed to study resource sharing among mobile operators as a solution to the interference problem, to use the resources more efficiently and to reduce the production cost

The main results were:

1- It is in the best interest of all mobile network operators to share their network and jointly invest in Long Term Evolution technology.

2- If the integration costs are four times as high as estimated or more, 'network sharing among all' is no longer attractive. In this case each Mobile Network Operator (MNO) should invest separately, but in all other cases the result remains the same.

3- If the investment in Long Term Evolution (LTE) is five times as high as estimated or more, Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) should not make an investment jointly or separately. In all other cases, the joint investment remains the most attractive option.

4- If Radio Access Network operational expenditures (RAN-OPEX) is less than half the amount estimated, the savings in operational expenditures due to sharing can no longer compete with the integration costs. In this case MNOs should invest separately. A higher RAN-OPEX will give more incentives to cooperate.

Study Ten

A PhD Thesis in Telecommunications titled “*Mobile Network Operators and Cooperation*” in 2011 from the Communications systems department, Royal institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden by Jan Markendahl.

The thesis aimed to propose, describe and analyze new mobile network concepts by answering the following research questions:

- 1- What are the main drivers for a specific type of cooperation?
- 2- In what ways can the actors organize the cooperation?

The main results were:

- 1-Cooperation can be between mobile network operators in infrastructure sharing.
- 2- Cooperation can be between mobile network operators and service providers such as SMS payments and point of sales.
- 3- Cooperation can be between network operator and customer such as exhibitions, hotels and malls.

Study Eleven

A Doctoral Dissertation in Telecommunications titled “*Cost Effective Deployment Strategies for Heterogeneous Wireless Networks*” in November 2007 from the KTH Information and Communication Technology, Stockholm, Sweden by Klas Johansson

The main contribution of this dissertation is a methodology to quantify the cost effectiveness of such heterogeneous networks and an evaluation of cost effective capacity expansion strategies for urban areas, the research questions were:

1. How to estimate the cost effectiveness of heterogeneous networks.

2. How radio resources should be shared between operators in a multi-operator cellular network.

The key requirements for radio resource management in multi-operator networks have also been identified. Researcher argued that a necessary requirement for effective resource sharing between competing actors is that their networks are business-wise decoupled. From this point of view, he observed that a common radio resource management across business boundaries should be designed carefully so that business critical information is not exchanged.

Study Twelve

A Master Thesis in Telecommunications titled “*Coopetition for innovative freight transport solutions in Swedish retail*” in 2013 from the Faculty of Engineering, Lund University, Sweden by Andreas Holmberg & Klas Örne.

The purpose of this master thesis is to test how a dyadic horizontal distribution cooperation affects the CO₂ emissions and costs for large grocery retailers in Sweden. In order to determine the effects, a supply chain design software needs to be used to build up the transport networks. A supporting analysis of which software is suitable has been done to facilitate the analysis of the effects of horizontal cooperation.

Research Question: Will the horizontal cooperation between the Swedish grocery retailing companies ICA and Coop reduce the CO₂ emission and the cost of transportation?

This master thesis has tested the concept in the grocery industry and the results show that ICA and Coop have a potential to lower the CO₂ emissions by 1% and reduce costs by 6.2%.

Study Thirteen

A Master Thesis in Business Administration titled “*Comparing the efficiency of competition strategy to coopetition strategy in managed care in South Africa*” in November 2008 from the Gordon Institute of Business Science, University of Pretoria by Stefan Roux.

The purpose of this research was to measure the difference in efficiency between a coopetition strategy and the competition strategy pursued in managed care firms in order to guide South African firms (MCO's) in their endeavors to ensure sustainable provisions of affordable, quality, accessible healthcare. The research question was: Would Coopetition strategy be proven more efficient?

And it has been proven that the coopetition strategy is more efficient than the competition strategy.

Study Fourteen

A Doctor of Philosophy dissertation in Management, competitiveness and development titled “*Competition, Cooperation, Co-opetition - Widening the perspective on Place Branding*” in 2012 from the Faculty of Social Science, Sant Anna School, Italy by Cecilia Pasquinelli.

The purpose of the study was to investigate a network of places cooperating under a single umbrella brand, the research questions were:

1. To what extent a network of places can be a brand? That is, to what extent a network of places can be shaped, conceived, perceived (brand image) as a brand?
2. To what extent network brands can foster re-branding effects?

The findings showed the extent to which a network brand can produce re-branding effects for those areas that cooperate under this umbrella (network) brand, by adding a new narrative without deleting the pre-existing ones concerning the single nodes of network.

Study Fifteen

A Master Thesis in Business Administration titled “*Coopetition Strategy management in SMEs - Case Study of Nyhammars and Bachstroms companies*” in Dec 2011 from the Faculty of Education and Economic Studies, University of Gavle, Sweden by Ruigun Chen and Zhiman Liang.

The purpose of this study was to analyze advantages and disadvantages of a coopetition relationship and then construct the critical success factors of

coopetition strategies for those small to medium-sized business (SMEs) who are interested or would use them in the future, the research questions were:

1. what are the advantages and disadvantages associated with coopetition strategy in SMEs?
2. What are the success factors of a coopetition strategy for SMEs?

The result showed that SMEs can achieve multiple benefits from a coopetition network. Strengthening technological capability and capturing more business opportunities are two key advantages. However, a coopetition strategy also hides potential risks such as opportunistic behavior, flowing out of customer information. A trusted relationship is the most important factor, compared with management commitment and communication management. Furthermore, holding high quality products is an important criterion for maintaining stability in the coopetition relationship.

Discussions on Previous Studies

The researcher came across fifteen different previous studies in the field of cooperation strategies, the studies can be summarized as:

1. One research studied the Reaction strategies in marketing and found that cooperation is less important, the researcher will study cooperation in telecom infrastructure and look for the effect of it.
2. Two researchers studied How the decision making is done and what are the benefits and barriers of cooperation.
3. Two researchers studied the entering strategy for the new operators to the market and found that cooperation is the best strategy for new entrants (joint venture)
4. Two researchers studied cooperation from cost perspective only and found that there would be a saving in CAPEX and OPEX and recommended that telecom operators invest and compete only on services.

5. One research studied the willingness of cooperation and found that operators are willing to cooperate with competitors over non-competitors and this looks not like our case so, the researcher will study the willingness in our environment.
6. Only one research studied the environmental effect of cooperation and found that it will help reducing environmental hazards but, in grocery market not in telecom market.
7. The recent researches studied the cooperation in Radio access networks and the fourth generation networks.

In this study the researcher will study some issues that are previously studied, but with considering the different environment and different culture of Sudan, like how the decision making regarding adopting cooperation strategies and the benefits and barriers.

Also will study the willingness to cooperate and the factors that affect cooperation. The researcher will search for the environmental effects of cooperation in the telecom networks which is missed by all examined studies.

The researcher will study the cooperation between the operators of fourth generation networks if implemented in Sudan. This technology is not yet implemented and all studies were done in Europe with different culture, economy and needs. However, at the time of writing up this thesis one operator started providing LTE services. A model will be proposed and applied to study the effect on CAPEX.

The researcher also will study the expected saving in foreign currency when applying cooperation strategies in telecom market in Sudan.

Also Sudan is a big country and it is very difficult to reach remote areas to deliver telecommunication services. The researcher will study the effect of cooperation on the ease or otherwise, speed and cost of covering remote areas.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Section one: Strategy and Strategic Management

Strategy Concepts and Definitions

The concept of strategy has been borrowed from the military and adapted for use in business. Many authors have traced the military genesis of the term strategy from the Greek and the Macedonians. The word 'strategos' began as a term describing a commanding role in the army and by the time of the Alexander the Great (330BC) had become the word which described the successful deployment of troops to overcome the enemy and to the system of governance which facilitated this planning⁽¹⁾.

If we asked someone to define strategy, likely we will be told that strategy is a plan, a direction, a guide, a course of actions into the future, a path to get from here to there. This definition called the intended strategy. Mintzberg et. al argue that this definition fails to recognize strategy as an emergent process, which is best seen as a pattern in a stream of decisions. Strategy for Mintzberg, is what emerges from actions rather than something planned in advance or in anticipation of future contexts.⁽²⁾

Liddell Hart presented a short definition of military strategy: "The art of distributing and applying military means to fulfill the ends of policy".⁽³⁾

Prahalad and Hamel, defined strategy as "A process for reinforcing intent by developing the core competences of a corporation, and leading and managing change".⁽⁴⁾

¹ John McGee, Howard Thomas, and David Wilson, *Strategy: Analysis and Practice* (Maidenhead, Berkshire: McGraw-Hill, 2005).

² Henry Mintzberg, *The Rise and Fall of Strategic Planning: Reconceiving Roles for Planning, Plans, Planners* (New York : Toronto: Free Press ; Maxwell Macmillan Canada, 1994), 25–35.

³ Basil Henry Liddell Hart, *Strategy*, 2nd rev. ed (New York, N.Y., U.S.A: Meridian, 1991).

⁴ Gary Hamel and C.K. Prahalad, "The Core Competence of the Corporation," 1990, 12.

The most common definition of strategy is defined by Harvard business historian Alfred D. Chandler in his book “strategy and structure” ⁽¹⁾ and it characterized strategy as “The determination of basic long-term goals and objective of an enterprise and the adoption of courses of action and the allocation of resources necessary for carrying out these goals”.

Quinn in a book entitled strategies for change: logical incrementalism, defined strategy as “The pattern or plan that integrates a firm’s major goals, policies and action sequences into a cohesive whole.

A well- formulated strategy helps to marshal and allocate a firm resources into a unique and viable posture based on its relative internal competences and short comings, anticipated changes in the environment and contingent moves by intelligent opponent”.⁽²⁾

Beside all these definition there are some common elements that can describe strategy as: ⁽³⁾

- ✓ Means of establishing firm purpose.
- ✓ A definition of the competitive domains of the firm and the firmal context.
- ✓ A response to the complexity of external opportunities and threats and internal strengths and weaknesses in order to achieve sustainable competitive advantage.
- ✓ A way to define managerial tasks and processes with corporate, business and functional perspectives.
- ✓ A system involving coherent, unifying and integrative systematic pattern of decisions.
- ✓ A definition of the economic and non-economic contributions which the firm intends to make to its stakeholders.

¹ McGee, Thomas, and Wilson, *Strategy*, 15.

² J.B Quinn, *Strategies for Change: Logical Incrementalism* (IL: Irwin: Homewood, 1980).

³ McGee, Thomas, and Wilson, *Strategy*. p 16

- ✓ An architecture to develop the distinctive competences of a firm.
- ✓ A vehicle to determine investments in tangible and intangible resources to develop the core capabilities which leads to sustainable advantages.
- ✓ An expression of strategic intent, stretching the firm innovates, leverage resources and develops new skills.

Types of strategy

Planned Strategy

Planned or deliberate strategies come about where there are precise intentions, which are written down and imposed by leaders. Key features include a large number of controls to ensure surprise-free implementation in an environment, which is controllable with manager who is able to ascertain, review and evaluate every option available, and they are able to choose what appears to be the best option in the light of rational criteria. Often there is a specialist strategy department. Firms using this strategy should be large enough to afford the cost of formal analysis and its goal should be operational. The environment in which the firm operates in must be reasonably predictable and stable. The firm should take a systematic and structured approach to its development, collect internal and external information and integrates decisions into a comprehensive strategy and focus on systematic analysis, particularly in the assessment of the cost and benefits of competing proposals.⁽¹⁾

Emergent strategy

Strategies can be deliberate or emergent strategies or a stage in-between.

There is a corporate intent followed by its implementation. Sometimes this intent is formally written down but emerges over time as part of the culture, as a series of related decisions, or when a firm develops its strategy it may find a need for changing the strategic course due to market conditions or missed criteria. The managers may make some decisions which will change the strategy direction.⁽²⁾

¹ Neil Riston, *Strategic Management* (Neil Riston & Ventusn publishing ApS, 2011), 20.

² Neil Riston, *Strategic Management* (Neil Riston & Ventusn publishing ApS, 2011), p. 21.

Figure 2.1: planned and emergent strategies

Source: Neil Riston, *Strategic Management* (Neil Riston & Ventusn publishing ApS, 2011), p. 22.

Opportunistic strategy

An Opportunistic investment strategy is one in which an investor or fund manager moves investments between different asset classes and investments on the basis of assessment of which have the greater potential to deliver superior returns at a particular point in time.⁽¹⁾

A firm may take advantage of changes in the environment or recognize new skills in opportunistic manner. Alternatively, firm may be set up by an entrepreneur because of an opportunity in the market place. Strategy is developed by significant bold decisions being made. Growth is the dominant goals of the firms, and in uncertain conditions, this type of strategy can result in the firm making significant gains.

Firm using this strategy suggest by it action that the environment is not flexible, it is a force to be confronted and controlled. Power is centralized in the chief executive, with an unwillingness to submit to authority.⁽²⁾

Imposed strategy

Strategy may be imposed on the firm. Government policies may have an impact on the strategy “this has been the case of public utilities that privatized”. Recession and threat of a takeover may force a strategy of cost cutting and

¹ “Fund Glossary - Client Portal - Client Portal,” accessed July 3, 2013, <http://clientservices.morningstar.com.au/display/Public/Fund%20Glossary>.

² Neil Riston, *Strategic Management* (Neil Riston & Ventusn publishing ApS, 2011), p. 22.

retrenchment. Technological developments may cause a firm to develop new products to replace the ones that have become obsolete.⁽¹⁾

Strategic Management

Strategic management can be defined as the art and science of formulating, implementing, and evaluating cross-functional decisions that enable a firm to achieve its objectives.

As this definition implies, the strategic management process means defining the organization's strategy. It is also defined as the process by which managers make a choice of a set of strategies for the organization that will enable it to achieve better performance. Strategic management is a continuous process that appraises the business and industries in which the organization is involved; appraises its competitors; and fixes goals to meet the entire present and future competitor's and then reassesses each strategy. The term *strategic management* is used to refer to strategy formulation, implementation, and evaluation, while *strategic planning* referring only to strategy formulation. The purpose of strategic management is to exploit and create new and different opportunities for tomorrow; *long-range planning*, in contrast, tries to optimize for tomorrow the trends of today.⁽²⁾

Strategic management process has four steps: Environmental Scanning, Strategy Formulation, Strategy Implementation and Strategy Evaluation.

Environmental Scanning

Environmental Scanning refers to a process of collecting, scrutinizing and providing information for strategic purposes. It helps in analyzing the internal and external factors influencing an organization. After executing the environmental analysis process, management should evaluate it on a continuous basis and strive to improve it.⁽³⁾ In section three of this chapter more information regarding the environmental scanning and analysis tools will be explained.

1 *ibid*, p. 22.

2 Fred R. David, *Strategic Management: Concepts and Cases*, 13th ed (Upper Saddle River, N.J: Prentice Hall, 2011), p. 6

3 'Strategic Management Process - Meaning, Its Steps and Components'

<<http://www.managementstudyguide.com/strategic-management-process.htm>> [accessed 21 June 2014].

Strategy Formulation

It is the process by which a firm chooses the most appropriate courses of action to achieve its defined goals. This process is essential to a firm's success, because it provides a framework for the actions that will lead to the anticipated results. Strategic plans should be communicated to all employees so that they are aware of the firm's objectives, mission, and purpose. Strategy formulation forces a firm to carefully look at the changing environment and to be prepared for the possible changes that may occur. A strategic plan also enables a firm to evaluate its resources, allocate budgets, and determine the most effective plan for maximizing ROI (return on investment).

A firm that has not taken the time to develop a strategic plan will not be able to provide its employees with direction or focus. Rather than being proactive in the face of business conditions, a firm that does not have set a strategy will find that it is being reactive; the firm will be addressing unanticipated pressures as they arise; and the firm will be at a competitive disadvantage.

Strategy formulation requires a defined set of six steps for effective implementation. Those steps are:

1. Define the firm business,
2. Define the strategic mission and vision,
3. Define the strategic objectives,
4. Define the competitive strategy,
5. Implement strategies, and
6. Evaluate progress.⁽¹⁾

Mission statement

Mission statement clarifies the purpose and primary, measurable objectives of the firm. Can be defined as "The unique purpose that sets a firm apart from others of

¹ ' BUS208-7.3.1.1-Strategy-Formulation-FINAL.pdf', p. 1 <<http://www.saylor.org>> [accessed 14 April 2014].

its type and identifies the scope of its operations in product, market and technology terms”.

That means it describes the firm’s product, market and technological areas and it does so in a way that reflects the values and properties of the firm strategic decision makers.

Firms can identify mission statement by concentrating in all or part of the following components: basic type of product or service to be offered, the primary market or customer group, the technology used, the firm’s fundamental concern for survival through growth, the firm’s managerial philosophy and the public image. ⁽¹⁾

Vision Statement

Presents the firm’s strategic intent that focuses the energies and resources of the company on achieving a desirable future. However, in actual practice, the mission and vision statements are frequently combined into a single statement. When they are separated, the vision is often a single sentence, designed to be memorable. ⁽²⁾

Strategy Implementation

Strategy implementation is "the process of allocating resources to support the chosen strategies". This process includes the various management activities that are necessary to put strategy in motion, institute strategic controls that monitor progress, and ultimately achieve organizational goals. ⁽³⁾

Strategy Evaluation

Strategy evaluation is the final step of strategy management process. The key strategy evaluation activities are: appraising internal and external factors that are the root of present strategies, measuring performance, and taking remedial /

¹ John A. Pearce and Richard B. Robinson, *Strategic Management: Formulation, Implementation, and Control*, 12th ed (New York: McGraw-Hill/Irwin, 2011), p 23,24.

² Ibid., 35.

³ “Strategic Management Process - Meaning, Its Steps and Components.”

corrective actions. Evaluation makes sure that the organizational strategy as well as its implementation meets the organizational objectives. ⁽¹⁾

These components are steps that are carried, in chronological order, when creating a new strategic management plan. Present businesses that have already created a strategic management plan will revert to these steps as per the situation's requirement, so as to make essential changes.

Figure 2.2: Components of Strategic Management Process

Source: <<http://www.managementstudyguide.com/strategic-management-process.htm>>

Components of Strategy:

A well-developed strategy contains five components, or sets of issues:

- a) *Scope*. The scope of a firm refers to the breadth of its strategic domain, the number and types of industries, product lines, and market segments it competes in or plans to enter. Decisions about a firm's strategic scope should reflect management's view of the firm's purpose or *mission*. This common thread among its various activities and product-markets defines the essential nature of what its business is and what it should be.
- b) *Goals and objectives*. Strategies should also detail desired levels of accomplishment on one or more dimensions of performance, such as volume growth, profit contribution, or return on investment over specified time.

¹ Ibid.

- c) *Resource deployments*. Every firm has limited financial and human resources. Formulating a strategy also involves deciding how those resources are to be obtained and allocated, across businesses, product-markets, functional departments, and activities within each business or product-market.
- d) *Identification of a sustainable competitive advantage*. One important part of any strategy is the specification of how *the firm will compete* in each business and product-market within its domain. How can it position itself to develop and sustain a differential advantage over current and potential competitors? To do so, managers must examine the market opportunities in each business and product-market and the company's distinctive competencies or strengths relative to its competitors.
- e) *Synergy*. Synergy exists when the firm's businesses, product-markets, resource deployments, and competencies complement and reinforce one another. Synergy enables the total performance of the related businesses to be greater than it would otherwise be: The whole becomes greater than the sum of its parts". ⁽¹⁾

Strategy Levels

Strategies exist at several levels in any firm - ranging from the overall business up to individuals working in it:

Corporate Strategy

Corporate level strategy is the highest level of strategy. It sets the long-term direction and scope for the whole firm. If the firm comprises more than one business unit, corporate level strategy will be concerned with what those businesses should be, how resources will be allocated between them, and how relationships between the various business units and between the corporate center

¹ "Marketingblog - 2.2 Three Levels of Strategy Similar Components but Different Issues," accessed July 4, 2013, http://marketingblog.wikispaces.com/2.2+Three+Levels+of+Strategy+Similar+Components+but+different+issues#cite_note-2.

and the business units should be managed. Firms often express their strategy in the form of a corporate mission or vision statement.⁽¹⁾

The principal concern of corporate-level strategy is to identify the industry or industries a firm should participate in to maximize its long-run profitability. A firm has several options when choosing which industries to compete in. First, it can concentrate on only one industry and focus its activities on developing business-level strategies to improve its competitive position in that industry. Second, a firm may decide to enter new industries in adjacent stages of the industry by pursuing a strategy of vertical integration, which means it begins to make its own inputs and/or sell its own products. Third, a firm can choose to enter new industries that may or may not be connected to its existing industry by pursuing a strategy of diversification. Finally, a company may choose to exit businesses and industries to increase its long-run profitability and to shrink the boundaries of the firm by restructuring and downsizing its activities.⁽²⁾

Business Unit Strategy

A strategic business unit (SBU) is a part of a firm for which there is a distinct external market for goods or services that is different from another SBU. The identification of a firm's SBUs helps the development of business level strategies since these may need to vary from one SBU to another⁽³⁾. It concerns more with how a business competes successfully in a particular market ,with strategic decisions about the choice of products, meeting needs of customers, gaining advantage over competitors, exploiting or creating new opportunities etc.⁽⁴⁾

It can be defined as " The plan of action that strategic managers adopt to use on firm's resources and distinctive competences to gain a competitive advantage over its rivals in a market or industry.

1 David Barnes, *Operations Management: An International Perspective* (CengageBrain. com, 2008), p. 22 .

2 Charles W. L Hill and Gareth R Jones, *Essentials of Strategic Management* (Mason, Ohio: South-Western/Cengage Learning, 2012), 162–163.

3 Gerry Johnson, Kevan Scholes, and Richard Whittington, *Exploring Corporate Strategy*. (Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall, 2008), 223.

4 Shubhangi Rajput, Shalini Singh, and Pratibha Singh, "Business Strategy, Change Management and Organizational Development," *VSRD International Journal of Business and Management Research* 2(2) (2012): 76.

The process of defining a business involves decisions about customer needs or *what* is to be satisfied, customer groups or *who* is to be satisfied and distinctive competences or *how* customer needs are to be satisfied.

These three decisions are the basis of the choice of a business-level strategy because they determine how a company will compete in an industry.⁽¹⁾

Operational Strategy

Also known as *Functional Strategy*, it is the development of a long-term plan for using the major resources of the firm for a high degree of compatibility between these resources and the firm's long term corporate strategy. Operations strategy addresses very broad questions about how these major resources should be configured to achieve the desired corporate and business unit's objectives.

Operations strategies are developed from the competitive priorities of a firm, which include (a) low cost, (b) high quality, (c) fast delivery, (d) flexibility , and (e) service.⁽²⁾

¹ Hill and Jones, *Essentials of Strategic Management*, 110.

² "Davis-01 - sample_ch2.pdf," 31–33, accessed July 8, 2013, http://highered.mcgraw-hill.com/sites/dl/free/0070922837/158533/sample_ch2.pdf.

Section Two: Competition and Competitors Relationships

Competitors

A competitor is any person or firm which is a rival against another. In business, a competitor is a company in the same industry or a similar industry which offers a similar product or service. The presence of one or more competitors can reduce the prices of goods and services as the companies attempt to gain a larger market share.

Competition also requires firms to be more efficient in order to reduce the cost⁽¹⁾

Different Relationships among Competitors (Inter firm Relationships)

Traditionally competitors have been said to only compete with each other but during the 90's of last century researches about strategic alliances have provided us with new insights into the different contents of relationships among firms that are embedded in an atmosphere of competition. There are four different types of relationships that can be developed among competitors depending on how firms interact with each other: *competition, co-existence, cooperation, and co-opetition*. In an atmosphere of competition, the competitors are linked to each other according to their relative positions.

Competition

Competition occurs when two or more products attempt to win over a common group of customers who are seeking a shared set of benefits offered by both products.

Co-existence

Competitors often strive for as little interaction as possible, which in some cases can give rise to a relationship of co-existence. The competitors know about each other; know the positions they have but do not challenge each other's positions. Therefore, the competitors seldom interact in rivalry with each other. The

¹ "What Is Competitor? Definition and Meaning," accessed July 15, 2013, <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/competitor.html>.

competitors are complementary partners, with well-defined and demarcated niches for their operations. However, these relationships are not permanent as the competitor's positions potentially are in conflict with each other. Some situations were found where competitors living in co-existence have started to compete, either because one of the competitors felt threatened by the other or because one of them saw the opportunity to expand their business into the competitor's domain.⁽¹⁾

Cooperation

Advantage may not always be achieved by competing. Cooperation between firms may be a way of achieving advantage or avoiding competition. Cooperation between potential competitors or between buyers and sellers is likely to be advantageous when the combined costs of purchase and buying transactions such as negotiating and contracting are lower through collaboration than the cost of operating alone.

Cooperation may be to increase selling power, increase buying power, build barriers to entry or avoid substitution, gain entry and competitive power and to share work with customers.⁽²⁾

Strategic Alliance

A strategic alliance is a particular mode of cooperation in which the partners make substantial investments in developing a long-term collaborative effort, and common orientation.⁽³⁾

¹ "Cooperation and Competiton Relationships - 4294.pdf," 3, accessed July 15, 2013, <http://impgroup.org/uploads/papers/4294.pdf>.

² Johnson, Scholes, and Whittington, *Exploring Corporate Strategy.*, 240–241.

³ David Faulkner, *International Strategic Alliances: Co-Operating to Compete* (London ; New York: McGraw-Hill, 1995).

Benefit of the Strategic Alliances

There are four potential benefits that international business may realize from strategic alliances: Ease of market entry, shared risks, shared knowledge and expertise and gaining competitive advantage. ⁽¹⁾

Types of Strategic Alliances

There are a lot of types of strategic alliances, which are listed below:⁽²⁾

Joint Ventures

A joint venture is an agreement between two or more parties to form a single entity to undertake a certain project. Each of the businesses has an equity stake in the individual business and share revenues, expenses and profits. Joint ventures between small firms are very rare, primarily because of the required commitment and costs involved.

Example of Joint Ventures: Tata and Fiat ⁽³⁾

In 2008 the Indian famous car manufacturer Tata and the Italian car manufacturer Fiat entered into a strategic alliance in which both sides will invest more than \$887 million through the rest of the decade to jointly make cars, engines, and transmissions at the Italian car manufacturer's plant in Ranjangaon in the western Indian state of Maharashtra. As a result of this cooperation a car with a very low price (about 2200 \$) will enter the market.

both car makers aim to jointly produce 100,000 vehicles and 200,000 engines and transmissions. Fiat and Tata are collaborating on a pickup that will be built by Fiat in Argentina and by Tata in India. Both will export their shared-platform pickup to Europe. Fiat's will have a more powerful 157-horsepower diesel engine built by Fiat, Tata will use its own 140-hp diesel engine.

1 Margarita ISORAITE, 'IMPORTANCE OF STRATEGIC ALLIANCES IN COMPANY'S ACTIVITY', 1(5) (2009), (pp. 39–46).

² Faulkner, *International Strategic Alliances*.

³ Nandini Lakshman and Gail Edmondson, "Tata and Fiat: Small Is Big in India," *BusinessWeek*, January 24, 2007, 1 and 2, www.businessweek.com.

In addition to serving the India market, the joint venture hopes to export cars to emerging markets in Latin America

Outsourcing.

The 1980s was the decade where outsourcing really rose to prominence, and this trend continued throughout the 1990s to today, although to a slightly lesser extent.

Affiliate Marketing

Has exploded over recent years, with the most successful online retailers using it to great effect. The nature of the internet means that referrals can be accurately tracked right through the order process.

Technology Licensing

This is a contractual arrangement whereby trademarks, intellectual property and trade secrets are licensed to an external firm. It is used mainly as a low cost way to enter foreign markets. The main downside of licensing is the loss of control over the technology – as soon as it enters other hands the possibility of exploitation arises.

Product Licensing

This is similar to technology licensing except that the license provided is only to manufacture and sell a certain product. Usually each licensee will be given an exclusive geographic area to which they can sell to. It is a lower-risk way of expanding the reach of your product compared to building your manufacturing base and distribution reach. Brand licensing is a commercial activity that involves the temporary transfer to a third party of the right to use a name, image, brand or logo which has been officially registered and which is protected by law

Good examples are the case of is the Coca Cola and Pepsi Cola.

Research and Development (R&D)

Strategic alliances based around R&D tend to fall into the joint venture category, where two or more businesses decide to embark on a research venture through forming a new entity.

Example of Research and Development AT&T , DEC and MIT(1)

The American Telephone and Telegraph (AT&T), Digital Equipment Corporation (DEC) and Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) had formed a pre competitive consortium to address the challenges of utilizing the evolving terahertz bandwidth capability of optical fiber technology to develop a national information infrastructure capable of providing flexible transport, common conventions and common servers.

Co-opetition

The term “co-opetition” was first introduced in 1993 by Raymond J. Noorda, founder and CEO of Novell Corp. Later, Adam Brandenburger, Professor at Harvard Business School and Barry Nalebuff, Professor at Yale School of Management adopted this term in their best seller book called “co-opetition” (Brandenburger and Nalebuff, 1996). According to these authors, co-opetition is defined as the combination of cooperation and competition for value creation. ⁽²⁾

“Co-opetition” is a model in which a number of stakeholders cooperate and compete to create maximum value; it is one of the most important business perspectives of recent years. Internet and mobile technologies have made it even more necessary for companies to both cooperate and compete, by enabling relationships through information sharing as well as integrating and streamlining processes. In today's networked economy, co-opetition is a powerful means of identifying new market opportunities and developing business strategy. ⁽³⁾

In a simple definition, co-opetition is defined as “simultaneously cooperation and competition between competitors for the same products”.⁽⁴⁾ Also Bengtsson and Kock defined co-opetition as “the dyadic and paradoxical relationship that

1 Stephen B Alexander and Donal Byrne, ‘Precompetitive Consortium on Wide-Band All Optical Network’, Journal of Light wave Technology, 11 (1993), p. 714.

2 DOROTHEA KOSSYVA, KATERINA SARRI and NIKOLAOS GEORGOPOULOS, ‘CO-OPETITION: A BUSINESS STRATEGY FOR SMES IN TIMES OF ECONOMIC CRISIS’, South-Eastern Europe Journal of Economics 1 (2014) 89-106, 2014, p. 91.

3 ‘Microsoft Word - p. 1 <http://www-07.ibm.com/services/pdf/the_value_of_relationships_in_the_networked_economy.pdf> [accessed 14 July 2013].

4 Bengtsson and M. and S. Kock, *Coopetition in Business Networks- To Cooperat and Compete Simultaneously.*, 29 (Industrial Marketing Management, 2000).

emerge when two firms cooperate in some activities, such as in a strategic alliance, and at the same time compete with each other in other activities is here called co-opetition”.⁽¹⁾

Co-opetition relationship between competitors depends on the activity related to customers. For instance, competitors cooperate in the activity which are far from customer as well as development of material, research and development; and compete in the activity close to customers such as sales and distributions. In other words, competition among firms exists on the market side and cooperates on recourses.⁽²⁾

There are two kinds of co-opetition for value creation; dyadic and network co-opetition. Dyadic co-opetition refers to the relationship between two competing business organizations whether on one or more levels of the value chain, while network co-opetition refers to the situation where more than two organizations cooperate and compete at the same time along one or more levels of the value chain.

Example one: Co-opetition

A notable example of dyadic co-opetition is the joint venture between Sony and Samsung called S-LCD for the development and production of 7th generation liquid crystal display (LCD) panels for flat screen TVs. This partnership was critical for both firms because they could not develop LCD technology in isolation. Both rivals contributed their technological capabilities in order to increase and lead the LCD TV market while each firm launched its own TV model in the market to appropriate a larger market share individually.

Example two: Co-opetition

Another example is the alliance between Apple Computer Inc. and Sony Corporation. The two global computer manufacturers formed an alliance in order

¹ Ibid.,p. 29

² “Competitive Advantage Definition | Investopedia.”

to carry out cooperative research and development (R&D) activities, so as to manufacture more powerful desktops and laptops.

Example three: Co-opetition

Another example is the case of SAP, the ERP software provider, which developed a business ecosystem consisting of clients, suppliers, other software providers and research institutions. The aim of this initiative was to create value for participating actors through the exchange of information and knowledge. Therefore, co-coopetitive relationships consist of two dimensions; value creation and value appropriation. The first dimension arises from cooperative activities while the second arises from competitive activities. Value creation derives from joint efforts with direct competitors who have complementary and relevant resources and capabilities.

Example four: Co-opetition

A 3G Infrastructure Services Company (AB) has been set up by telecom operators Hi3G Access and Europolitan Vodafone in order to share network infrastructure during the built-out of 3G UMTS networks in Sweden. 3G Infrastructure Services AB's had built and now operating a network that covers 70% of the Swedish population.

Hi3G Access and Europolitan Vodafone have equal stakes in the new company. Each partner in the joint venture has been granted 3G licenses to provide 3G service to almost 100% of the Swedish population. In August 2001 Nokia and Europolitan Vodafone signed an agreement for the delivery of UMTS networks for Europolitan Vodafone.

Nokia's 3G infrastructure is based on open standards, platforms and interfaces for a smooth evolution to commercial 3G services. It includes integrated end-to-end solutions, including charging, security, network management and service control applications.

Nokia already offers a full range of support services and solutions to help network providers differentiate in today's fast-changing business environment and rapidly build out 3G networks.⁽¹⁾

There are many examples of network co-opetition as well, such as the joint venture among Nokia, Sony Ericsson, Samsung, and Psion called Symbian for the creation of an operating system to compete against traditional computer companies.

Competitive Advantage

It is an advantage that a firm has over its competitors, allowing it to generate greater sales or margins and/or retains more customers than its competitors. There can be many types of competitive advantages including the firm's cost structure, product offerings, distribution network and customer support.⁽²⁾

In order to survive and prosper in an industry, firms must meet two criteria: they must supply what customers want to buy, and they must survive competition. A firm's overall competitive advantage derives from the difference between the value it offers to customers and its cost of creating that customer value. Competitive advantages give a firm an edge over its rivals and an ability to generate greater value. The more sustainable the competitive advantage, the more difficult it is for competitors to neutralize the advantage.⁽³⁾

Creating and Sustaining Competitive Advantage

Firms that try to achieve competitive advantage hope to preserve it over time and much of what is written about competitive strategy takes the need for sustainability as a central expectation. There are different positions in a market where customers have different 'requirements' in terms of value-for-money.

¹ "Todays Breaking 3G News ... by 3G ... World Leading 3G Telecoms Portal," accessed April 10, 2014, <http://www.3g.co.uk/ZPR1153.htm>.

² "Competitive Advantage Definition | Investopedia," accessed July 9, 2013, http://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/competitive_advantage.asp.

³ "Layout 1 - Value Chain Analysis.pdf," 2, accessed July 9, 2013, <http://www.imanet.org/PDFs/Public/Research/SMA/Value%20Chain%20Analysis.pdf>.

These positions also represent a set of generic strategies for achieving competitive advantage. Since these strategies are 'market-facing' it is important to understand the critical success factors for each position. ⁽¹⁾

Price-based strategies

A firm pursuing competitive advantage through low prices might be able to sustain this in a number of ways:

1. *Operating with lower margins* may be possible for a firm either because it has much greater sales volume than competitors.
2. *A unique cost structure*. Some firms may have unique access to low-cost distribution channels, be able to obtain raw materials at lower prices than competitors or be located in an area where labor cost is low.
3. *Firm specific capabilities* may exist for a firm such that it is able to drive down cost throughout its value chain.
4. *Focusing on market segments* where low price is particularly valued by customers but other features are not. An example is the success of dedicated producers of own-brand grocery products for supermarkets. They can hold prices low because they avoid the high overhead and marketing costs of major branded manufacturers.

There are, however, dangers with trying to pursue low-price strategies because *Competitors may be able to do the same*. There is no point in trying to achieve advantage through low price on the basis of cost reduction if competitors can do it too, or customers may start to *associate low price with low product/service benefits*.⁽²⁾

Differentiation-based Strategies

The aim is to achieve competitive advantage by offering better products or services at the same price or enhancing margins by pricing slightly higher. The

¹ Johnson, Scholes, and Whittington, *Exploring Corporate Strategy*, 232–232.

² "Strategy Explorers," accessed July 9, 2013, <http://www.strategyexplorers.com/>.

success of a differentiation approach is likely to be dependent on the following key factors:

1. Identifying and understanding the strategic customer.
2. Identifying key competitors.
3. The difficulty of imitation.
4. The extent of vulnerability to price based competition.⁽¹⁾

Strategic lock-in

Another approach to sustainability, whether for price-based or differentiation strategies, is the creation of strategic lock-in. This is where a firm achieves a proprietary position in its industry, it becomes an industry standard.⁽²⁾

Responding to Competitive Threat

The preservation of competitive advantage in the face of competitors who attack by targeting customers on the basis of a different competitive strategy can be a serious threat. One of the most common is low-price competitors entering markets dominated by firms that have built a strong position through differentiation.⁽³⁾

Resource based view

Many definitions of strategy define strategy as the alignment of organizational processes and resources with desired objectives, as in the definitions showed in section one of this chapter, like Alfred D. Chandler definition “The determination of basic long-term goals and objective of an enterprise and the adoption of courses of action and the allocation of resources necessary for carrying out these goals”. The field of strategic management focuses on understandings sources of sustained competitive advantages for firms. A variety of factors have been proved to have an important impact on the ability of firms to acquire sustained competitive advantage. The relative cost position of a firm, the ability of firms to cooperate in

¹ Johnson, Scholes, and Whittington, *Exploring Corporate Strategy.*, 233.

² Ibid., 234.

³ Ibid., 236.

strategic alliances and a firm's ability to differentiate its products can be some of these factors.⁽¹⁾

Resource based view is an approach to achieving competitive advantage, it examines the relation between a firm's internal characteristics and performance. Using this theory, the potential of firm resources to generate sustained competitive advantage is analyzed. It is based on the assumption that strategic resources are heterogeneously distributed across the firms (heterogeneous) and this distribution is stable over time (immobile). The firm resources that are considered are the physical capital resources, the human capital resources and the organizational capital resources. In order a firm's resource to generate sustained competitive advantage for the firm should be valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable. A resource is valuable if it helps the firm to implement strategies that increase its efficiency and effectiveness. A resource is rare when it is not possessed by many firms whereas a resource is inimitable if firms that do not possess this resource cannot obtain it. In order a resource to be non-substitutable, it should not have strategically equivalent valuable resources that are not rare or imitable.⁽²⁾

¹ Barney, J. B. (1991). Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage. *Advances in Strategic Management*, pp. 203-225.

² Barney, J. B. Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage.

Section Three: Environments and Analysis Tools

Strategy Environment

Environments of strategy are the factors to be analyzed in order the firm to survive and thrive as conditions develop and change around it. These conditions are known as the external environment and comprise a wide range of factors, including the characteristics of the industry and market, the political conditions, the economic future, the technological future, the regulation and competition. The environmental analysis will enable the firm to develop its strategic plan through an examination of the external environment in which the firm is operating. An examination of internal environment will enable a firm to translate the strategic plan into a corporate plan for implementation. ⁽¹⁾

Strategic Analysis

Strategic Analysis is "the process of conducting research on the business environment within which a firm operates and on the firm itself, in order to formulate strategy or a theoretically informed understanding of the environment in which a firm is operating, together with an understanding of the firm's interaction with its environment in order to improve the firm's efficiency and effectiveness by increasing the firm's capacity to deploy and redeploy its resources intelligently ⁽²⁾.

Examples of analytical methods used in strategic analysis are SWOT* analysis ,PEST** analysis, Porter's five forces analysis , Four corner's analysis, Value chain analysis, Early warning scans, War gaming, Game Theory and GAP Analysis.

In this section SWOT, PEST and the competition strategy analysis tools porter four corners and game theory are explained.

¹ Neil Riston, *Strategic Management* (Neil Riston & Ventus publishing ApS, 2011), pp. 25–30.

² Jim Downey, *Strategic Analysis Tools* (Topic Gateway Series, 2007), 3.

* Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

* * Political, Economic, Socio-Cultural, and Technological changes

Game theory will be used in the practical part of the research to help choosing between the two strategies (compete or co-opete)

SWOT Analysis

SWOT Analysis is a useful technique for understanding firm's Strengths and Weaknesses, and for identifying both the open Opportunities and the Threats that facing the firm. Used in a business context, a SWOT Analysis helps to carve a sustainable niche in the market. Used in a personal context, it helps you develop your career in a way that takes best advantage of your talents, abilities and opportunities.

What makes SWOT particularly powerful is that, it can help the firm uncover opportunities that are well placed to exploit. And by understanding the weaknesses of the business, the firm can manage and eliminate threats that would otherwise catch it unawares.

More than this, by looking inside the firm and its competitors using the SWOT framework, firm can start to craft a strategy that helps to distinguish from its competitors, so that it can compete successfully in its market.⁽¹⁾

When using SWOT analysis, it should be ensured that Only specific, verifiable statements are used and the internal and external factors are prioritized so that time is spent concentrating on the most significant factors. This should include a risk assessment to ensure that high risk or high impact threats and opportunities are clearly identified and are dealt with in priority order.

The analysis should be implemented at the business activity level rather than at a total company level, which may be less actionable, and the tool should not be used in an exclusive manner. No one tool is likely to be completely comprehensive, so a mixture of option-generating tools should be used.⁽²⁾

¹ "SWOT Analysis - Strategy Tools from MindTools.com," accessed July 4, 2013, http://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newTMC_05.htm.

² Jim Downey, Strategic Analysis Tools (Topic Gateway Series, 2007), p. 6.

Example: Dell Computer SWOT Analysis ⁽¹⁾

In the mid-1990s, Dell Computer used a SWOT analysis to create a strong business strategy that has helped it become a very strong competitor in its industry value chain. Dell identified its strengths in selling directly to customers and in designing its computers and other products to reduce manufacturing costs. It acknowledged the weakness of having no relationships with local computer dealers. Dell faced threats from competitors such as Compaq and IBM, both of which had much stronger brand names and reputations for quality at that time. Dell identified an opportunity by noting that its customers were becoming more knowledgeable about computers and could specify exactly what they wanted without having Dell salespersons answer questions or develop configurations for them. It also saw the internet as potential marketing tool. The results of Dell's SWOT analysis are:

Strengths

1. Sell directly to consumers
2. Keep costs below competitors' costs

Weaknesses

1. No strong relationships with computer retailers

Opportunities

1. Consumer desire for one-stop shopping
2. Consumers know what they want to buy
3. Internet could be a powerful marketing tool

Threats

1. Competitors have stronger brand names
2. Competitors have strong relationships with computer retailers.

The strategy that Dell followed after doing the analysis took all four of the SWOT elements into consideration. Dell decided to offer customized computers built to

1 'SWOT Analysis Example' <<http://som.csudh.edu> [accessed 19 February 2014].

order and sold over the phone, and eventually, over the internet. Dell's strategy capitalized on its strengths and avoiding relying on a dealer network. The brand and quality threats posed by Compaq and IBM were lessened by Dell's ability to deliver higher perceived quality because each computer was custom made for each buyer.

PEST Analysis

PEST Analysis is a simple and widely used tool that helps the firm analyze the Political, Economic, Socio-Cultural, and Technological changes in the business environment. This helps to understand the forces of change that firm is exposed to, and, from this, takes advantage of the opportunities that they present.⁽¹⁾

The factors that should be studied in PEST analysis are :⁽²⁾

Political factors: Include government regulations such as employment laws, environmental regulations and tax policy. Other political factors are trade restrictions and political stability.

Economic factors: The factors that affect the cost of capital and purchasing power of a firm. Economic factors include economic growth, interest rates, inflation and currency exchange rates.

Social factors: Factors that has an impact on the customer's need and the potential market size for a firm's goods and services. Social factors include population growth, demographics and attitudes towards health.

Technological factors: These influence barriers to entry, make or buy decisions and investment in innovation, such as automation, investment incentives and the rate of technological change.

¹ "PEST Analysis - Problem-Solving Training from MindTools.com," accessed July 7, 2013, http://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newTMC_09.htm.

² Jim Downey, *Strategic Analysis Tools*, 27.

PEST factors can be classified as opportunities or threats in a SWOT analysis. It is often useful to complete a PEST analysis before completing a SWOT analysis⁽¹⁾.

PEST Analysis is useful for four main reasons:

1. It helps to spot business or personal opportunities, and it gives an advanced warning of significant threats.
2. It reveals the direction of change within the business environment. This helps to shape what the firm is doing, so that it can work with change, rather than against it.
3. It helps to avoid starting projects that are likely to fail, for reasons beyond control.
4. It can help to break free of unconscious assumptions when entering a new country, region, or market; because it helps to develop an objective view of this new environment.⁽²⁾

Example: General Electric Company (GE) PEST Analysis ⁽³⁾

Political

As a multinational company, General Electric has to deal with political systems of different nations. In spite of some of the countries presenting favorable environment for business survival and growth, others present difficult conditions. Tax systems and regulations also differ across countries and so does the level of government intervention in business activity.

For example, in United States, the Internal Revenue Authority requires companies to submit tax returns annually on April 15, Government intervention is minimal and the business environment is much favorable. Political stability can also be said to be reasonable so that business survival is highly probable.

¹ Jim Downey, Jim Downey, Strategic Analysis Tools (Topic Gateway Series, 2007), p. 7.

² "PEST Analysis - Problem-Solving Training from MindTools.com."

³ "PEST Analysis of General Electric Company," accessed February 19, 2014, <http://richet.hubpages.com/hub/PEST-Analysis-of-General-Electric-Company>.

These conditions may not apply in other countries such as China and Singapore where government control over businesses is high.

Economic

Fluctuations in interest rates, exchange rates and money value greatly affect activities and operations of General Electric. Factors such as deflation and inflation as well as government spending in different countries in which General Electric has ventured often influence business productivity and profitability.

The economic impacts caused by the current economic crisis are being felt all over the world. General Electric has recorded decreased sales mostly due to lower lending rates by banks. In addition to that, prices of inputs have also risen considerably.

Social

Norms, culture, religion and social set-ups often determine how a business should conduct itself in a particular country or environment. In the different countries which General Electric has ventured into, the company is faced by different socio-cultural challenges which influence its corporate culture to a very large extent. The culture in a particular country determines the working hours, employment policies, procedures for appointing managers and the type of goods to be produced. Similar to other multinational companies, General Electric has to contend with such issues and deal with them effectively.

Technological

Technology in the modern world is advancing at an enormous pace. Innovative products are always being introduced using more advanced technology each day. Older technology is therefore getting outdated at a very high rate across all sectors in the economy. Aimed at outdoing competitors, many companies have turned to innovation, research and development which have brought about improved levels of technology. The rate of technology advancement globally varies with each country that General Electric has invested in as they vary in terms of resources

available. Among the countries with the highest rate of technology advancement are United States and Japan which General Electric has ventured into.

As a result of multinational companies having to deal with different sets of political, economic, socio-cultural and technological aspects, designing a PEST analysis exclusive to General Electric was almost impractical. It is however notable that there are some factors that are universal among countries.

Technology constitutes one of these factors and a closer look at the PEST analysis reveals that technology is advancing at a very high pace globally. Multinational companies like General Electric must therefore be on the lookout to ensure that their technology is up-to-date when new forms are introduced in the market. Some economic factors such as global crises which lead to increase in interest rates and decrease in bank lending capacity are also universal. Conducting a PEST analysis aids a company in understanding the business environment better so as to facilitate the better planning and resource allocation to maintain high productivity and profitability.

Four corner's analysis

Four corners' Analysis, developed by Michael Porter, is useful for analyzing competitors and determining their course of action. It emphasizes that the objective of competitive analysis should be on generating insights into the future, and calls for understanding what motivates the competitor. The "four corners" refer to four diagnostic components essential to competitor analysis: *future goals*, *current strategy*, *assumptions* and *capabilities*.⁽¹⁾

The model can be used to develop a profile of the likely strategy changes a competitor might make and how successful they may be and to determine each competitor's probable response to the range of feasible strategic moves other competitors might make in addition to the competitor's probable reaction to the

¹ "Analysis | COS," accessed July 7, 2013, <http://www.cosxo.com/analysis/>.

range of industry shifts and environmental changes that may occur. The four corner are:⁽¹⁾

Future Goals: Analysing a competitor's goals assists in understanding whether they are satisfied with their current performance and market position. This helps predict how they might react to external forces and how likely it is that they will change strategy.

Management assumptions: The perceptions and assumptions that a competitor has about itself, the industry and other companies will influence its strategic decisions. Analysing these assumptions can help identify the competitor's biases and blind spots.

Current strategy: A company's strategy determines how a competitor competes in the market. However, there can be a difference between 'intended strategy' (the strategy as stated in annual reports, interviews and public statements) and the 'realised strategy' (the strategy that the company is following in practice, as evidenced by acquisitions, capital expenditure and new product development). Where the current strategy is yielding satisfactory results, it is reasonable to assume that a firm will continue to compete in the same way as it currently does.

Capabilities: The goals, assumptions and strategy of a firm will determine the nature, likelihood and timing of a competitor's actions. However, a firm's capabilities will determine its ability to initiate or respond to external forces.

¹ Riston, *Strategic Management*. p

Figure 2.3: Summary of Porter's four corner's analysis

Source: Analysis | COS' <<http://www.cosxo.com/analysis/>>

Example: General Electric (GE) Four Corner's Analysis ⁽¹⁾

GE's Assumptions

About GE

- Diverse portfolio mixture = economic stability & superior positioning supplemented by acquisitions.
- GE is able to solve China's infrastructure issues and satisfy Chinese government regulations.
- Able to acquire and retain top talent.
- An industrial company first, a financial/capital lending company second
- An R&D powerhouse/ innovative technology and services company

¹ 'GE Four Corners Analysis' <<http://www.slideshare.net> [accessed 19 February 2014].

- GE is a global company and will win if political culture is fair – the playing field might change.

About the Industry/Competitors

- Clean energy and infrastructure will be high growth markets
- Growth drivers will come equally or more from developing countries as from West.
- Support from Chinese civic leaders not exclusive nor permanent
- China will continue to seek commercial smart grid solutions to offset industrial pollutants.

GE's Capabilities

Strengths

- Global reach, industry excellence and dominance across multiple sectors
- Brand recognition and reputation is sterling
- Diversified product portfolio and balanced revenue streams
- Energy Infrastructure Expertise (23% of 2009 rev.)
- Strong presence in growth markets specifically China (Smart Grid Demonstration Center) 60% of sales are overseas
- Clean energy innovator – Ecomagination (2005)

Weaknesses

- Dependence on third parties for raw materials
- High debt burden
- Historically dependent on mergers and acquisitions
- Lack of international experience in Smart Grid implementation

Competencies

- Emerging market penetration
- Company-to-Country Approach
- Integrating Acquired Firms into GE Structure

- Worldwide Multi-industry network – strong adjacencies
- Proven energy generation, transmission/distribution, efficient end use
- Technical proficiency and vertically integrated manufacturing and distribution of products.

GE's Current Strategy

GE Corporate Current Strategy

- Divest in financial lending – maintain high liquidity – jump on strategic growth opportunities
 - Clean Energy
 - Infrastructure
- Strong Investment in Infrastructure
 - “long-term growth through building out adjacencies”
 - “There will be more than \$10 trillion invested in infrastructure by 2015, with a significant portion in emerging markets.”
- Strategic technology-advancing partnerships with Intel, Google, Eli Lilly and Company.
- Demonstration Center with 100,000 sq. ft. space in Yangzhou already implemented
- Awards \$55 million to 12 companies competing in Smart Grid Contest to speed updates
- Ecomagination plan
 - GE pledged to increase the revenues in Ecomagination to more than \$25 billion by 2012
- Continue to increase global presence (China, India)

GE's Future Strategy

Product: Provide the most comprehensive end-to-end solutions to win \$100b smart grid industry.

- GE's ability to work within the Chinese business and government communities is equally important as technical prowess.

- Chinese firms will likely make a play to own all or part of a multinational player; GE may have to consider selling a stake in its business or partnering with a Chinese firm.
- GE needs to understand the strategic difficulties of Chinese nationalism in the guise of domestic firms and re-think market strategy to win support from Chinese business community.
- Transmission capacity must be increased exponentially to meet Chinese market demand. This must be weighed with the likelihood of the Chinese to comply or reject global carbon emissions initiatives and carbon pricing. The smart grid will expand fastest if Chinese policy supports carbon reduction.

Promotion: Partner with local Chinese companies and be willing to provide all culturally acceptable incentives to win government support for GE products AND negotiate with competitors where needed.

Price: GE has stated goal of seven percent annual growth and a 20% market share of Smart Grid business.

Place (Distribution): Continue to expand demonstration centers such as the Yangzhou facility in 2nd tier cities across the country to earn market share, brand loyalty and municipal favor.

Game Theory

Game theory is a branch of applied mathematics and economics that studies strategic situations where there are several stakeholders, each with different goals, whose actions can affect one another. Although it has been applied to complex business issues and military strategy, game theory reveals its card-game origins through its name and terminology. For example, a game is any situation where multiple players can affect the outcome, a player is a stakeholder, a move or option is an action a player can take and, at the end of the game, the payoff for each player is the outcome.

In general, the value of game theory lies in understanding the interactions and likely outcomes when the end result is dependent on the actions of others who have potentially conflicting motives. Game theory's value to business lies in allowing structured analysis of complex multi-player issues including the identification of a business' best attainable outcome, threats and promises available to different players and the prediction of the likely actions and reactions of other players. Game theory with its focus on the interactions of multiple players, each trying to maximize their own rewards, is a natural fit for many types of business issues. From labor negotiations to competitive pricing, game theory provides a structured way to analyze the set of possible strategies and recommend an optimal strategy for each player.⁽¹⁾

1 'Microsoft Word - Tom Mitchell
<http://www.rijpm.com/pre_reading_files/Open_Options_Introduction_To_Game_Theory.pdf> [accessed 7 July 2013].

Chapter Three

Telecommunications Networks and Telecommunications in Sudan

Telecommunications Networks

A telecommunications network is a collection of terminal nodes, links and any intermediate nodes which are connected to enable communication between the terminals.

The transmission links connect the nodes together. The intermediate nodes use switching techniques to pass the signal through the correct links and terminal nodes to reach the correct destination terminal.

Each terminal in the network usually has a unique address so messages or connections can be routed to the correct recipients. The collection of addresses in the network is called the address space.

Examples of telecommunications networks are:

1. Computer networks
2. The Internet
3. The telephone network (land lines and mobile)

Telecommunication Network Components

All telecommunication networks are made up of basic components that are present in each network environment regardless of type or use.

These basic components include terminals, telecommunications processors, telecommunications channels, computers, and telecommunications control software.

1. Terminals are the starting and stopping points in any telecommunication network environment. Any input or output device that is used to transmit or receive data can be classified as a terminal component.⁽¹⁾ For example, a telephone is a terminal.

2. Telecommunications channels are the way by which data is transmitted and received. Telecommunication channels are created through a variety of media of which the most popular include copper wires and coaxial cables (structured cabling) and wireless radio frequencies. Fiber-optic cables are increasingly used to bring faster and more robust connections to businesses and homes. Nodes equipped with a number of channels, switch the information received along these links to direct it towards its terminal node.
3. Telecommunications processors support data transmission and reception between terminals and computers by providing a variety of control and support functions.

Telecommunication Backhaul

The backhaul portion of the network comprises the intermediate links between the core network, or backbone network and the small sub networks at the "edge" of the entire hierarchical network. Mobile phones communicating with a single tower constitute a local sub network, the connection between the tower and the rest of the world begins with a backhaul link to the core of the service provider's network.

Access network

It is that part of a telecommunications network which connects subscribers to their immediate service provider. It is contrasted with the core network, which connects local providers to each other.

Core network

Network core, is the central part of a telecommunication network that provides various services to customers who are connected by the access network. One of the main functions is to route telephone calls.

The core network provides many functions such as authentication, call control and switching, Service Invocation and Gateway.

Typical 2nd and 3rd Generation Mobile Network Architecture

A typical Mobile Network in 2nd and 3rd generations consist of three main parts:

1. Base Station Subsystem
2. Network Switching Subsystem
3. Backhaul

Base Station Subsystem

The base station subsystem (BSS) is the access part of the Mobile telephone network and it is responsible for handling traffic and signaling between a mobile phone and the Network Switching subsystem. The base station subsystem (BSS) consist of two main parts the Base Transceiver Station (BTS) and the Base Station Controller (BSC).

Base Transceiver Station (BTS)

The base transceiver station, or BTS, contains the equipment for transmitting and receiving radio signals (transceivers), antennas, and equipment for encrypting and decrypting communications with the base station controller (BSC).

Base transceiver station sites (towers) are the structures, e.g. towers, concrete columns, rooftop masts, and where BTS are installed. By site of installation, these can be divided into ground-based towers (GBT) and rooftop towers

Figure 3.1: BTS Site components

Source: Researcher

Base station Controller (BSC)

Typically, a BSC has tens or even hundreds of BTSs under its control. The BSC handles allocation of radio channels, receives measurements from the mobile phones, and controls handovers between BTSs.

Network Switching Subsystem (NSS)

Network switching subsystem (NSS) (or core network) is the component of a system that carries out call switching and mobility management functions for mobile phones roaming on the network of base stations. It manages the setup, opening, switching and transfer of voice and data communication channels, and the gateway switches that function to route calls, etc. across telephone network or other mobile telecommunications networks.

The core network and the access network are generally known as “active infrastructure”. It is owned and deployed by mobile phone operators and allows mobile devices to communicate with each other and telephones in the wider public switched telephone network (PSTN). The architecture contains specific features and functions which are needed because the phones are not fixed in one location.

The NSS originally consisted of the circuit-switched core network, used for traditional services such as voice calls and short messages (SMS). It was

extended with an overlay architecture to provide packet-switched data services known as the general packet radio service (GPRS) core network. This allows mobile phones to have access to services such as multimedia messages (MMS) and the Internet.

Components of the subsystem are:

Mobile Switching Centre (MSC), it is the primary service delivery node for the mobile system, responsible for routing voice calls and SMS as well as other services (such as conference calls, FAX and circuit switched data). The MSC sets up and releases the end-to-end connection, handles mobility and hand-over requirements during the call and takes care of charging and real time pre-paid account monitoring.

The home location register (HLR), is a central database that contains details of each mobile phone subscriber that is authorized to use the core network. There can be several logical, and physical, HLRs per public land mobile network (PLMN), The HLRs store details of every Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) card issued by the mobile phone operator. Each SIM has a unique identifier called an International mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) which is the primary key to each HLR record.

The authentication center (AuC), function is to authenticate each SIM card that attempts to connect to the core network (typically when the phone is powered on). Once the authentication is successful, the HLR is allowed to manage the SIM and services described above.

The visitor location register (VLR), is a database of the subscribers who have roamed into the area of the MSC (Mobile Switching Center) which it serves. Each main base station in the network is served by exactly one VLR, hence a subscriber cannot be present in more than one VLR at a time. The data stored in the VLR has either been received from the HLR, or collected from the MS (Mobile station). In practice, for performance reasons, most vendors integrate the VLR directly to the V-MSC and, where this is not done, the VLR is very tightly linked

with the MSC via a proprietary interface. Whenever an MSC detects a new MS in its network, in addition to creating a new record in the VLR, it also updates the HLR of the mobile subscriber, appraising it of the new location of that MSC.

Gateway MSC (G-MSC), is the MSC that determines which MSC the subscriber who is being called is currently located at. It also interfaces with other networks. All mobile to mobile calls and other networks to mobile calls are routed through a G-MSC.

Figure 3.2: The relation between BSS and Core subsystems

Source: Mobile Networks Tutorial, white paper www.jdsu.com. accessed august 30 2013.p3

Typical 4th Generation LTE Mobile Network Architecture

LTE stands for Long Term Evolution and commonly marketed as 4G LTE, it is a standard for wireless communication of high-speed data for mobile phones and data terminals.

LTE is a registered trademark owned by ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) for the wireless data communications technology and a development of the GSM/UMTS standards. However other nations and companies do play an active role in the LTE project. The goal of LTE was to increase the capacity and speed of wireless data networks using new DSP (digital

signal processing) techniques and modulations that were developed around the turn of the millennium. A further goal was the redesign and simplification of the network architecture to an IP-based system with significantly reduced transfer latency compared to the 3G architecture.

The high-level network architecture of LTE is comprised of following three main components:

1. The User Equipment (UE).
2. The Evolved UMTS Terrestrial Radio Access Network (E-UTRAN).
3. The Evolved Packet Core (EPC).

The User Equipment (UE)

The internal architecture of the user equipment for LTE is identical to the one used by UMTS and GSM which is actually a Mobile Equipment (ME). The mobile equipment comprised of the following important modules:

1. Mobile Termination (MT): This handles all the communication functions.
2. Terminal Equipment (TE): This terminates the data streams.
3. Universal Integrated Circuit Card (UICC): This is also known as the SIM card for LTE equipment's. It runs an application known as the Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM).

The E-UTRAN (The access network)

The E-UTRAN handles the radio communications between the mobile and the evolved packet core and just has one component, the evolved base stations, called eNodeB or eNB. Each eNB is a base station that controls the mobiles in one or more cells. The base station that is communicating with a mobile is known as its serving eNB.

LTE Mobile communicates with just one base station and one cell at a time and there are following two main functions supported by eNB:

1. The eNB sends and receives radio transmissions to all the mobiles using the analogue and digital signal processing functions of the LTE air interface.
2. The eNB controls the low-level operation of all its mobiles, by sending them signalling messages such as handover commands.

The Evolved Packet Core (EPC) (The core network)

The Home Subscriber Server (HSS) component has been carried forward from second and third generations and is a central database that contains information about all the network operator's subscribers.

The Packet Data Network (PDN) Gateway (P-GW) communicates with the outside world i.e. packet data networks PDN.

The serving gateway (S-GW) acts as a router, and forwards data between the base station and the PDN gateway.

The mobility management entity (MME) controls the high-level operation of the mobile by means of signaling messages and Home Subscriber Server (HSS).

The Policy Control and Charging Rules Function (PCRF) is a component which is responsible for policy control decision-making, as well as for controlling the flow-based charging functionalities in the Policy Control Enforcement Function (PCEF), which resides in the P-GW.

Backhaul

The term backhaul may be used to describe the entire wired part of a network, although some networks have wireless instead of wired backhaul, in whole or in part, for example using microwave bands and mesh network topologies that may use a high-capacity wireless channel to get packets to the microwave or fiber links.

A mixture of microwave and optical transmission network can be used to implement a mobile network backhaul, but normally an optical transmission

network is used to connect the distributed base transceiver stations with their respective base station controller.

The optical transmission network consists of two parts:

The optical fiber cable , an optical fiber (or optical fibre) is a flexible, transparent fiber made of high quality extruded glass (silica) or plastic, slightly thicker than a human hair. It can function as a waveguide to transmit light between the two ends of the fiber. Optical fibers are widely used in fiber-optic communications, which permits transmission over longer distances and at higher bandwidths (data rates) than other forms of communication. Fibers are used instead of metal wires because signals travel along them with less loss and are also immune to electromagnetic interference.

The Optical Transmission Equipment, also known as the optical add-drop multiplexer (OADM) is a device used in telecommunication systems for multiplexing and routing different channels of light into or out of a single fiber . This is a type of optical node, which is generally used for the construction of optical telecommunications networks. "Add" and "drop" here refer to the capability of the device to add one or more new channels to an existing signal, and/or to drop (remove) one or more channels, passing those signals to another network path. An OADM may be considered to be a specific type of optical cross-connect.

Infrastructure

It is the basic physical structures and facilities (e.g. buildings, roads, power supplies) needed for the operation of a society or enterprise.⁽¹⁾

In general terms, infrastructure comprises the physical structures that support the operation and functioning of an enterprise or community. Within a community, infrastructure can be separated into categories of economic infrastructure (including water and sewerage, transport, energy distribution and information and

1 'Infrastructure: Definition of Infrastructure in Oxford Dictionary (British & World English)' <<http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/infrastructure>> [accessed 14 July 2013].

communication networks) and social infrastructure (including matters such as schools, police, hospitals and recreation facilities).

Telecommunications Infrastructure

Telecommunications infrastructure for mobile network primarily consists of:

1. Active infrastructure: covers all the electrical elements of infrastructure like lit fibre, access node switches, broadband remote access servers, spectrum, antennas, Transceivers and Microwave equipment.
2. Passive infrastructure: covers all the non-electrical or civil engineering elements of infrastructure such as towers, BTS shelters, cables, power Supply, Generators, Batteries, Air-conditioners and Fire extinguishers.
3. Backhaul: includes core network elements such as switching centers, GPRS service nodes, transmission equipment and all links connecting elements of the core network.⁽¹⁾

Resource based view and cooperation in telecom infrastructure

Infrastructure is a physical capital resource. According to the already presented resource based view, infrastructure can lead to sustained competitive advantage if it is valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable. Infrastructure is a valuable resource for the network operator since its use is a precondition for the provision of mobile services. If cooperation in building or sharing infrastructure does not take place then we can also claim that it is rare, inimitable and non-substitutable. Considering the high investments costs, the required upgrade costs and constant investments we can realize that taking the decision of building a mobile network infrastructure from the scratch is not that easy and entails many risks. This fact makes the mobile network infrastructure rare even though radio spectrum licenses for the new technologies are not rare. If cooperation in infrastructure does not

¹ 'Passive-Infrastructure-Sharing-in-Telecommunications.pdf', p. 1
<<http://www.kpmg.com/BE/en/IssuesAndInsights/ArticlesPublications/Documents/Passive-Infrastructure-Sharing-in-Telecommunications.pdf>> [accessed 14 July 2013].

take place, then the actors that do not own it cannot use it, that means that infrastructure is also inimitable. Mobile network infrastructure is used for the provision of mobile services. Many of these services can be acquired using internet. However, the context of using mobile services by accessing mobile network infrastructure differs from the context of using services by accessing internet. In other words, mobile service market and internet market provide different things to the end users. For this reason, the network infrastructure is non-substitutable for the things that it provides. All in all, if cooperation in infrastructure does not take place infrastructure constitutes a source of sustained competitive advantage.

By applying cooperation in building or sharing infrastructure to the main assumption of the resource based view i.e. resources are heterogeneous and immobile is not in place, two out of the four empirical indicators of the potential of firm resources to generate sustained competitive advantage, the rareness and inimitability are lost. If cooperation takes place, then infrastructure does not constitute a source of sustained competitive advantage. Based on resource based view, we can conclude that the network operators are not willing to accept (providing or receiving) any form of infrastructure sharing, regardless of the category, so as to avoid losing a source of sustained competitive advantage i.e. network infrastructure.

Infrastructure Based Vs Service Based Competition

In Telecommunication's network industries, two regulatory means can be chosen to introduce competition:

Infrastructure based competition, whereby operators are incited to invest in infrastructure and fully compete on both the infrastructure access market (upstream or wholesale market) and on services delivered through infrastructure (downstream or retail market).

Service based competition, whereby service providers have an equal and nondiscriminatory access to a unique monopolized infrastructure, is considered an essential facility and required to offer services in.

Types of Cooperation in mobile networks infrastructure

The types of cooperation or usage that apply to mobile network infrastructure can be broken down as follows:

Mobile Virtual Network Operator (MVNO)

Is a company that provides telecommunications services but does not build its own network infrastructure. In other words, an MVNO leases the mobile infrastructure for its operations from a mobile network operator (MNO) rather than developing its own network, adding functions to the telecommunications services it provides to subscribers.

Roaming

The second type of joint ownership or usage is roaming. Roaming refers to the use of another MNO network for certain areas and services by companies that have built their own mobile network infrastructure and provide telecommunications services

Telecommunications Infrastructure Sharing

Building Telecommunications networks requires high investments, which leads to high mobile-service prices. Telecommunications infrastructure sharing is one of the alternatives for lowering the cost of network deployment, especially in rural, less populated or economically marginalized areas.⁽¹⁾

Passive infrastructure sharing

Passive infrastructure sharing allows Telecommunications network operators to share the non-electrical, civil engineering elements of telecommunication networks. This might include rights of way or easements, fiber and copper cables,

¹ 'Executive Summary - Trends08_exec_A5-E.pdf', p. 15 <http://www.itu.int/ITU-D/treg/publications/Trends08_exec_A5-e.pdf> [accessed 14 July 2013].

ducts, pylons, masts, trenches, towers, poles, equipment rooms and related power supplies, air conditioning, and security systems.

Active infrastructure sharing

Active infrastructure sharing involves sharing the active electronic network elements embodied in base stations and other equipment for mobile networks and access node switches and management systems for fiber networks. Sharing active infrastructure is a much more contested issue, as it goes to the heart of the value-producing elements of a business. Many countries have restricted active infrastructure sharing out of concern that it could enable anti-competitive conduct, such as collusion on prices or service offerings. In addition, for some remote and less accessible areas, the risks of active infrastructure sharing have to be balanced against the alternative of having no services at all.⁽¹⁾

¹ 'Executive Summary - Trends08_exec_A5-E.pdf', p. 13.

Figure 3.3: Types of Cooperation in mobile networks infrastructure

Figure 3.4: Infrastructure sharing Components

Forms of Cooperation in infrastructure sharing

Site sharing/collocation

This is the basic form of sharing where operators agree to share available infrastructure, including site space, buildings and easements, towers and masts, power supply, and transmission equipment.

Site sharing is suitable for densely populated areas with limited availability; expensive sites such as underground subway tunnels; and rural areas with high transmission and power costs. ⁽¹⁾

¹ Isabelle Gross, 'Infrastructure Sharing and LLU' (presented at the CoE/ARB Workshop, Khartoum, Sudan, 2011), p. 13.

Network sharing

Sharing BTS equipment and sharing common networks, operators typically share the radio equipment, mobile services switching center, visiting location register (MSC/VLR), and serving GRPS support node (SGNSN)

Each operator keeps its own individual home network that has subscriber databases, services, subscriber billing and connections to external networks.⁽¹⁾

Spectrum sharing

Spectrum sharing also known as spectrum trading. It entails operators to lease their spectrum to other operators on commercial basis

Spectrum is a scarce resource ; it is often underused by one operator in a given area and sharing is viable option for two or more operators.⁽²⁾

Towers companies

Set up of new independent company that manage BTSs or selling the operator's tower to another company to manage it. This situation will allow fair treatment of new entrant and cash injection for operators selling their sites.

Example one: Tower companies

Tower sale nets Cell C 430m

MOBILE network operator Cell C has sold its cell phone towers to American Tower Corporation for 430m in a sale and leaseback agreement.

Cell C had previously announced its intention to sell its towers and then lease them from the buyer. Cellphone companies are looking at sharing towers to offset some of the capital and operational expenditure of infrastructure roll-outs.

The proceeds from the transaction will also boost Cell C's cash position, as it has been burdened by interest-bearing debts that drain cash each month, contributing to the company's failure to make a net profit.

¹ Isabelle Gross, p. 14.

² Isabelle Gross, p. 15.

The sale involves 1400 of Cell C's towers, and up to 1800 additional towers that are either under construction or will be constructed over the next two years. Cell C will be the anchor tenant on each of the towers being purchased.⁽¹⁾

Examples Two: Tower companies

In October 2010, GSM operator Vodafone Ghana agreed to outsource the operation and management of its 750 cell towers to Eaton for 10 years. This is expected to reduce Vodafone Ghana's costs and improve and widen its coverage, while Eaton is investing USD80 million in the cell sites over the period of the contract. Eaton will also be able to lease spare capacity to other operators in Ghana, improving efficiency in that market.

Recently, on signing the tower sharing deal, Phutuma Nhleko, former CEO of the MTN Group, said that infrastructure sharing makes absolute sense. "We have in the recent past looked at various permutations to reduce our infrastructure roll out costs and the ongoing costs of operating our passive infrastructure in our key markets."²

¹ 'Tower Sale Nets Cell C 430m | Archive | BDlive' <<http://www.bdlive.co.za/articles/2010/11/08/tower-sale-nets-cell-c-430m;jsessionid=ECABD36A02915A1A33862395090AA661.present1.bdfm>> [accessed 10 April 2014].

² " | KPMG | GLOBAL," 2, , <https://home.kpmg.com/xx/en/home/>. [accessed March 23, 2015].

Section two: Telecommunications in Sudan

Background

Sudan had his first telecommunications facility in mid- nineteenth century with the construction of the telegraph link between Cairo and Sawaken in 1859, to Kassala in 1871 then Khartoum in 1873. A small administration for Posts and Telegraph was then established. First telephone switch was established in El-Dabba in 1892. First telephone switch in Khartoum was in 1903⁽¹⁾. Since that time, the entity in charge of telecommunication had undergone a number of firmal restructuring changes. All forms of entities established were government-owned that remained, for all practical purposes, entities without little or no operational and financial autonomy and little control over their own destiny.

Despite many development plans and efforts, the state of telecommunication sector in the country remained extremely poor up to 1994. By that time, Sudan had one of the lowest penetration rates (0.23%) even by regional standards. ⁽²⁾

The privatization era

The Three-Year liberalization programme which has been known as the Economic Salvation Programme (1990–1993), adopted by the Government of Sudan, emphasized the role of telecommunications in the socio-economic development process and called for the removal of the monopolistic environment in the sector and for the involvement of the private sector-whether local or foreign-in the telecommunication sector as well as in other sectors of the economy in an endeavor to overcome the persistent shortfalls in investment and performance.

The Sudan Telecommunications Public Corporation(STPC) was privatized in November 1993⁽²⁾ and Sudan Telecommunication Company , Sudatel, has been,

¹ The Regulatory Authority for Information and Telecommunications, *The Book of Telecommunications*, 1 (Sudan: The Regulatory Authority for Information and Telecommunications, 2009), p. 11.

² The Regulatory Authority for Information and Telecommunications, p. 12.

established instead, with major shares and management control now held by Etisalat of the UAE and Qatar Telecom. It is also listed on several regional stock exchanges. The company presided over the world's fastest growing fixed-line market until it started substituting traditional copper lines with CDMA2000 fixed-wireless access in 2005.

The network operation & service provision had been separated from the regulatory functions. An independent regulator (the National Telecommunications Corporation) had been launched in 1996.

The mobile telephone service was first introduced by the Sudan Mobile Telephone Company -Mobitel owned by Sudatel 60% and several stakeholders 40% in 1997.

Table 3.1: Licensed Telecom Operators

Name	Date of License	Date of Commercial Operation	Type of Service
Sudan Telecom Co., plc (Sudatel)	April 93	February 94	National fixed service
Sudatel Group, plc (Sudatel/Sudani)	Feb 2005 Unified License	Feb 2006	National fixed & mobile 3G – CDMA
Canar (Etisalat), private company	October 2004 April	2005 National	Limited mobility, NGN
MTN – Sudan private company	Nov 2003	Sept 2004	National mobile 3G - GSM
Zain-Sudan (formerly Mobitel) private company	1996	Feb 97	National mobile 3G - GSM

Source: The Regulatory Authority for Information and Telecommunications, p. 23.

Sudatel is facing Competition in the fixed-line market from Canartel (Licensed in 2004) which, interestingly, is also majority-owned by Etisalat. It too opted for CDMA2000 technology to cost effectively roll out fixed services and, like Sudatel, is offering wireless broadband services through this network.

The use of fixed-line was rapidly increasing till 2005 and by launching Canar service it was proposed to continue increasing but the wide use of mobile phones affected it and the number of fixed-lines started decreasing with high rate.

Table 3.2: Fixed line Subscribers in Sudan in thousands

Year	1995	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Sudatel	67	672	937	1029	670	412	200	85	66	237	171	79	95
Canar					105	149	245	274	297	304	313	317	320
Total	67	672	937	1029	775	561	445	359	363	541	484	395	415

source: NTC official web site' <<http://www.ntc.gov.sd>> and Central Bureau of Statistics, Statistical Monitoring (Sudan, 2012), p. 163.

Figure 3.5: Fixed line Subscribers in Sudan in thousands

source: Source: researcher from NTC data

Sudatel exited the mobile market when it sold its GSM network to Celtel (now Zain) in 2006, following the arrival of competition the year before from Bashair Telecom (now MTN). Sudatel then re-entered the mobile market independently with its CDMA network under the brand name Sudani. At the end of 2009 the company launched a GSM-based network overlay, keeping up with Zain and MTN in offering third generation services including mobile broadband.⁽¹⁾

Table 3.3: Mobile Subscribers in Sudan in millions

Year	1998	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Zain	0.01	0.21	0.53	1.05	2.21	2.75	3.89	5.16	7.5	10.25	13	12.56	11.73	11.40
MTN					0.23	1.03	2.09	2.65	3.77	3.47	6.03	7.90	8.73	8.95
Sudani						0.9	2.24	3.25	3.07	4.37	6.08	7.30	6.82	7.44
Total	0.01	0.21	0.53	1.05	2.44	4.68	8.22	11.06	14.34	18.09	25.11	27.76	27.28	27.80

source:

- NTC official web site' <<http://www.ntc.gov.sd>> and
- Central Bureau of Statistics, p. 163.

¹<http://www.budde.com.au/Research/Sudan-Telecoms-Mobile-and-Broadband.html#sthash.USsWIXoH.dpuf> accessed august 15 2013

Figure 3.6: Mobile Subscribers in Sudan in millions

source: Source: researcher from NTC data

Table 3.4: Mobile and Fixed Subscribers in Sudan in millions

Year	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Fixed	0.67	0.94	1.03	0.67	0.41	0.20	0.09	0.07	0.24	0.17	0.79	0.95
Mobile	0.21	0.53	1.05	2.44	4.68	8.22	11.06	14.34	18.09	25.11	27.76	27.28
Total	0.88	1.47	2.08	3.11	5.09	8.42	11.15	14.41	18.33	25.28	28.55	28.23

source: NTC official web site' <<http://www.ntc.gov.sd>> and Central Bureau of Statistics, p. 163.

Figure 3.7: Mobile and Fixed Subscribers in Sudan in millions

source: Source: researcher from NTC data

Until the end of 2011 the competition was as follows

- Sudatel and Canartel competing in the fixed line market, whole sale of transmission capacities and wireless broadband services
- Sudatel, Zain and MTN competing in mobile services

By the end of the 2011 Zain started building its own fiber network.

Figure 3.8: Market Share of mobile Services

Source: researcher from NTC data

Figure 3.9: Market Share of fixed-line Services

Source: researcher from NTC data

The Internet

The Internet in Sudan started in 1998 as a joint venture between Sudan Telecommunications Company (SUDATEL) and the Sudan Corporation of Broadcasting and Television as a dial-up service. Many Internet service providers were licensed since that time, but most of them shrink due to the decline of the telephone fixed service and the increase of the mobile.

The total number of internet users in Sudan reached 10,129,606 by the end of the of the September 2014.

Table 3.5: Mobile internet market share in Sudan

Operator	Share	Percentage
Zain	4,645,317	45.86%
MTN	3,484,289	34.40%
Sudani	2,000,000	19.74%
Total	10,129,606	100%

Source: National Telecommunication Corporation

Current Telecommunication Networks

In order to offer the above mentioned telecommunication services and serve these millions of subscribers, the telecom companies built networks that covers many parts of the country, for fiber networks all the companies except MTN had laid thousands of kilometers of fiber.

Sudatel, the biggest fiber backbone owner has laid around 6000 kilometers while Canar the second owner had laid around 2800 kilometers and Zain around 2400 kilometers.

Beside the telecom companies, some governmental entities also had laid some private fiber networks, table (3.6) shows fiber lengths in Sudan.

Table 3.6: Fiber lengths

No	Entity	Fiber length km
1	Sudatel	5948.31
2	Canar	2782.7
3	Zain	2408
4	Sudanese Electricity Transmission Company - SETCO	4998
5	Ministry of Petroleum	2492

Source: NTC

The following figures represent the fiber roots for Sudatel, Canar, Zain and SETCO

Figure 3.10: Sudatel Fiber roots

Source: Researcher from NTC data

Figure 3.11: Fiber roots of SETCO

Source: Researcher

Figure 3.12: Fiber roots of Canar

Source: Researcher from NTC data

Figure 3.13: Fiber roots of Zain

Source: Researcher from NTC data

For mobile network sites the three mobile telecom operator had constructed thousands of sites covering different parts of the country. In order to serve its subscribers Zain built around 2239 sites 650 of them in Khartoum state, MTN built around 2045 sites and Sudatel built around 1450 sites.

Cooperation data received from Zain and MTN, but the researcher could not get it from Sudatel, Zain implemented cooperation in about 70 sites which is about 3% of the total sites, MTN implemented sharing in about 10 sites, Zain shared sites with Sudatel, TV broadcast and oil company's telecom towers, while MTN shared only SETCO sites.

Telecommunication Sector Structure

The structure of the telecommunication sector in the country at present is as follows:

1. The Ministry (Ministry of Information & Communications):
In charge of policies and legislations.

2. The Regulator (National Telecom Corporation, NTC):
In charge of regulatory functions.
3. The Licensed operators and service providers:
In charge of the operation of licensed networks and of the provision of the service.
4. National Information Centre:
In Charge of e-government and Informatics
5. Sudan Corporation for Broadcasting and Television:
In charge of the Media content regulation and Transmission
6. Consumers and civil society groups:
consultation.

Regulation Body

The need for regulation varies depending on the conditions of the marketplace. While the design of the regulatory framework may differ, certain critical elements should be included in an effective regulatory framework, such as the functional aspects of the regulatory authority; decision-making processes; accountability; consumer protection, dispute resolution and enforcement powers. Consideration and proper implementation of these features are key elements for creating an enabling

environment for development of the sector and for increased consumer welfare.

In the 1990s, many countries introduced the first wave of reform by privatizing their national operators. Until that time, telecommunications services were largely provided under monopoly conditions and thus limited regulation existed because the government was acting as both operator and regulator. In the very initial stages of liberalization, some countries have created a regulator when introducing a private monopoly.

These regulators oversee the sector and ensure that the private operator knows and can comply with the —rules of the game. In the second wave of liberalization,

which sometimes occurs simultaneously with privatization, governments typically authorize the entry of new service providers and new services into the market.

Generally, this involves the modification of the licensing framework in order to allow the entry of the new players, as well as the introduction of complementary rules and regulations to allow these operators to participate in the marketplace. The third wave of liberalization occurs when the incumbent operator 's exclusivity period ends and full competition can be introduced. With the introduction of full competition, the role of the regulator actually increases , particularly during the early stages of transition from the former monopoly to effective competition.⁽¹⁾

Role of regulator

Telecom Regulatory Authority is an independent regulating body to regulate the telecommunications business in a certain country. Its mission is to ensure that the interests of consumers are protected and at the same time to nurture conditions for growth of telecommunications, broadcasting and cable services in a manner and at a pace which will enable telecom operators to play a leading role in the emerging global information society. It should frame various policies and regulation to ensure that consumer will get maximum benefits of services offered by various service providers.

One of the key functions of the regulator is to regulate Price fixation as Telecom operators have to follow guidelines issued from it from time to time in relation to tariff for basic telephony, cellular services, Data services, cable services, etc.

Another key function of the regulator is to issue guidelines for telecom operators in relation to standards for quality of service on regular basis.

¹ Colin Blackman and Lara Srivastava, *Telecommunications Regulation Handbook*, Tenth Anniversary Edition (The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank, InfoDev, and The International Telecommunication Union, 2011), pp. 9–10.

National Telecommunication Corporation (NTC)

National Telecommunications Corporation of Sudan (NTC) was founded in September 1996 with a vision to provide an effective regulatory framework and adequate safeguards needed to ensure fair competition and protection able to fulfill the consumer interests.

NTC, as governmental body, is committed to perform its functions independently and effectively as a regulator body with a comprehensive authority.

The headquarters of NTC is in Khartoum State, and it has the right to establish branches in different States of the Sudan.

NTC is acting under communication Minister's direct supervision in executing its duties, fulfilling its functions and exercising its powers in accordance with the principal directions issued by the minister which aim to develop the media, information, and wired and wireless telecommunication systems.⁽¹⁾

NTC Responsibilities

The Corporation shall have the following functions and powers:

- Implementation of the country's national strategy related to the telecommunication sector.
- Lay down the plans, policies and regulations for the provision of the telecommunication services and their establishment thereof on the national level taking into consideration the balanced development and the service of the social and national objectives.
- Approve the methods and cost of telecommunication services and regulate the tariffs of the services in coordination with entities providing such services and supervise them thereafter.

¹ 'NTC official web site' <<http://www.ntc.gov.sd/index.php/ar/>> [accessed 13 April 2014].

- License the operation in the different fields of services and activities of telecommunications.
- Lay down the bases for the regulation, allocation and licensing the of the frequencies for wireless equipment, wireless systems and broadcasting stations, taking into consideration the security aspects relating.
- Coordinate with the competent entities in relation to the assembly, import and manufacture of the different equipment and materials of the telecommunication systems.
- Set specifications of the systems, terminals and equipment used in the field of telecommunications and establish the necessary measurements and test procedures.
- Protect the obligations of the State and requirements thereof in the field of national security ,and defense, emergencies and regional and international policies in co-ordination with the entities providing the telecommunication services .⁽¹⁾

Telecommunications Strategy in Sudan

Quarter Century National Strategic Plan

National Council for Strategic Planning in Sudan developed a quarter century (2007-2031) national strategy for the telecommunication sector, this strategy aims to improve telecommunications services, reduce the communication gap across the country and regionally and leads Sudan to play a role the international telecom traffic.

1. Telecommunications development in the country and following the technological developments.
2. Introducing the various types of communications services across the country with a high degree of reliability, quality and appropriate price.

¹ 'NTC Official Web Site'.

3. Encourage investment in various fields to promote fair competition.
4. Fixed phone for every five citizens.

This strategy has been divided into five phases in each phase a part of the strategy will be achieved.⁽¹⁾

Phase one (2007-2011)

1. Encouraging investment in the sector.
2. Continuous training of the human resources.
3. Gaining experience and keep abreast of technological developments.
4. Spreading of the telecommunications culture.
5. Control and Monitoring tools update.
6. The spread of communications to reach one phone for every 30 citizens and introducing mobile communications to rural areas to reach one phone for every 75 citizens.
7. Increase the capacity of international gateways to receive incoming and outgoing traffic and link the neighboring countries with the Arab world and the activation of e-commerce.⁽²⁾

Phase two (2012-2016)

1. Continue to build capacity.
2. Gain experience and continuous development.
3. Create a wide regional and international relations.
4. The development of fixed and mobile telecommunications services.
5. Increasing the number of phones according to the proportion of the population up to one telephone per 20 citizens.
6. The introduction of mobile communications to rural areas. One mobile phone for every 50 citizens.

¹ 'National Council for Strategic Planning' <<http://www.ncsp.gov.sd/>> [accessed 5 October 2014].

² 'National Council for Strategic Planning'.

7. Using the telecommunications for the benefit of society, economically and socially.
8. Feasibility study for the satellite Sudanese studies.
9. Activation of e-commerce.⁽¹⁾

Phase 3 (2017-2021)

1. Development of the human resources by continuity of training.
2. Continue building foreign relations.
3. Connect the neighboring countries and the expansion of e-commerce.
4. Connect Africa and the Arab world.
5. Modernization and development of control and monitoring tools and adapted to serve the national security.
6. Renewal and revision of investment laws to keep up with new developments in the world of communications and to create a healthy climate for competition.
7. Raise fixed phones (one for every 15 citizens) and one mobile phone for every 30 citizens.⁽²⁾

Phase 4(2022-2026)

In this phase of the strategy NTC shall review the previous phases to ensure:

1. Completion of all the remaining items from the previous strategy phases
2. continue to develop human resource capabilities.
3. follow the updates in technology
4. Update and Increase the capacity of international gateways.
5. Raise fixed phones (one for every 5 citizens).
6. Encouraging investment in the sector with the latest control tools.
7. New technologies and Knowledge transfer to Sudan.

¹ 'National Council for Strategic Planning'.

² 'National Council for Strategic Planning'.

8. Entering the world of satellite with fixed and insight steps.
9. Spreading of the telecommunications culture all over the community.⁽¹⁾

Phase 5 (2027-2031)

1. Development of the capabilities and human resources is completed at the highest levels to engage in a half-century stage.
2. Completion of a fixed base and modern systems to compete in the investment field.
3. full connectivity to Africa and the Arab world.
4. Proliferation of satellite services.
5. The spread of mobile communications services.
6. Contribution in the technical development of the neighboring countries.⁽²⁾

NTC Strategy

After the completion of phase 1 and evaluating it, NTC has developed its strategy for phase 2 and it states:

1. Using telecommunications and postal services to improve the policies that control communications and post in the country according to a known measurement indicators and support decision making by providing the appropriate information to reach a sustainable development, stability and prosperity.
2. Expand telecommunications, Internet and data services.
3. Human resources and institutional capacity building.
4. Localization of the software industry in Sudan.
5. Activation of universal access services.

¹ 'National Council for Strategic Planning'.

² 'National Council for Strategic Planning'.

6. Issuing and amending laws needed to keep up with technology shifts.
7. Tighten coordination between the partners in the field of communication and information.
8. Quality Assurance in the field of communication and information.⁽¹⁾

Policies support Cooperation

The National Telecommunication Corporation (NTC) has issued on July 2012 regulatory guidelines to encourage cooperation in infrastructure sharing and explained that the main purposes of the guidelines were:

1. Minimizing operators CAPEX and OPEX.
2. Allowing operators to use the reduced CAPEX and OPEX in introducing new services and promoting their competitive position.
3. Reducing broadband networks cost especially in rural areas.
4. Customer benefits (good service with lower prices).
5. Minimizing environmental, health and community hazards.
6. Reducing market entry barriers and supporting introduction of new services.
7. Utilization of the current resources by preventing duplication.
8. To be sure that environmental benefits achieved by sharing will be used for general benefits.
9. Balance between exclusivity and open access.

NTC laid some rules for the operators to implement infrastructure sharing like:

1. The infrastructure owner should be neutral, transparent, fair in competition and not apply discrimination between operators.
2. The owner and seeker should enter direct negotiation and the agreement should be based on suitable pricing models.

¹ 'NTC Official Web Site'.

3. Operators should publish on websites and other media the details of existing as well as future infrastructure installations available for sharing by other service providers and update the data in quarter year basis.
4. Review and validate existing agreement with 60 days.
5. Any operator can reserve 25% of its infrastructure for future use.

Observations on Telecommunications Sector Strategy

1. The strategy stated only objectives, no detailed plans or responsibility matrix to show who is responsible of implementing each objective.
2. Some objective has been achieved before their estimated time, but still not updated in next phase eg. Number of phone per no of people.

Chapter Four

Research Methodology and field work

Introduction

The concepts of cooperating in strategy implementation and telecom infrastructure sharing both are considered as new terminologies in Sudan many operators are more unwilling to cooperate in building or sharing infrastructure. Hence, there were no previous research about the profitability of this model here in Sudan. Though, it has proved successful in other international contexts, it is still necessary to test its practicability and profitability in the Sudanese market.

Research Methodology

This section deals with means and techniques through which data was collected for this research thesis. The primary data collected here were meant for testing and validating the prior hypotheses postulated through literature review, which is the secondary source

Data Collection Strategies

This research thesis is case study based and the cases reviewed are the current cooperation in strategy implementation between telecom operators either by building together or sharing existing infrastructure.

Data for the thesis are collected from different resources:

- literature review
- National Telecommunication Corporation
- Telecom Operators
- Site Survey
- Interviews

Field work

This part contained real cooperation situation, an interview with telecommunication field experts and a model of an LTE network.

Cooperation real situation

In this part of the study the researcher studied the current cooperation in implementing telecom companies' strategies either by building stations together or using stations owned by one company by another, in addition to real cases of cooperation in building fiber optic networks.

Site Survey

The first practical part of this research was a survey done to study the current situation of cooperation between telecom operators in Sudan and its effect on the operation and capital expenditures.

The selection of the areas to be surveyed was done taking into consideration that they should cover the areas where cooperation is considered to be implemented because of the low number of subscribers and the difficulties of normal operation processes such as routine visits, emergency maintenance visits, high energy cost and high cost of communication links.

Example of such areas are highways and medium to small size cities. Khartoum – Port Sudan highway was chosen as an example of highways and Atbara city was chosen as an example of medium size cities. Reasons of selecting Khartoum – Port Sudan road were: i) It was the first highway covered by telecom services. ii) more than 45% of the road length crosses nonresidential areas while other roads were designed to pass by residential areas. iii) this road is the most important in the country so all operators will try building their networks to get customer satisfaction. While Atbara was chosen because it is in the center of the road and that will reduce the survey cost.

A trip from Khartoum city to Port Sudan in the Eastern part of Sudan was done to study on site the cooperation levels in collocation of sites between telecom operators on the high way, and in Atbara city as an example for highway and cities.

Usually in highways in Sudan the number of telecom service users is too low because highways normally pass unpopulated areas .and the cost of delivering the service is higher than urban areas for many reasons like:

- No power source, so they have to use generator sets or solar cells.
- It is difficult to link the sites and if telecom links are available their cost is high.
- The cost of routine visits, maintenance and fuel feeding is too high.

So in most cases companies do not get profit from serving customers in such areas, to minimize the cost in such areas companies have to look for solutions, one of the solution is to use solar cells instead of generator set, this solution can help minimizing the operation cost (Fuel and frequent site visits for the generator), but its initial cost is higher compared with the generator cost, the capital cost of site includes; land rent, civil work, tower, power system , cooling system , security ..etc. This cost can be minimized if two or more operators agreed to use the same site to install their equipment.

The main purpose of this site survey was to study to which degree cooperation is implemented in the areas where it is applicable.

The trip from Khartoum to Port Sudan is approximately 800 kilometers, it took from the researcher two days to complete the trip, each communication site in the highway was registered and a photo was taken, the data collected in the survey were as follows:

1. Number of towers in the same area
2. Distance between adjacent towers in the same area in kilometers

3. Distance from previous tower
4. Power source type

The following tables show the data collected in the first day from Khartoum to Atbara about 350 kilometers and the data collected in the second day of the trip from Atbara to Port Sudan around 460 kilometers

Real Cooperation Cases

In this part real cases of implementing companies' strategies are shown, in the first case cooperation is done between a telecom operator (MTN) and the Sudanese Electricity Transmission company (SETCO), SETCO is not a telecom operator but it operates a private telecom network owned by the ministry of Electricity and Irrigation and used for operation of electricity network and energy sale.

The second case of cooperation is between the telecom operator (Zain) and the telecom operator (Canar). Although both companies are telecom operators, but really they are not competitors. Zain is a mobile service operator and Canar is a landline operator, Canar has built its own fiber network and started connecting the western states and for special reasons its network stopped at Elobied city around 600 kilometers south – west of the capital city Khartoum, Zain had a license to erect fiber cables in the western states, Zain erected more than 2000 kilometers of fiber cables in western states and its network covers from Elobied to Genena within Chad borders. Zain was planning to the western states from Elobied to the country's capital city Khartoum, but Zain project stopped for many reasons such as license and high cost.

Interview

Introduction

As already presented in chapter three, cooperation can lead to savings. We need to realize whether savings or strategic considerations are more important. In order

to do so, the main drivers, barriers and trade-offs of cooperation should be investigated.

Interviews are conducted so as to test and explore possible new benefits, barriers and trade - offs of applying cooperation strategies between competitors in the telecommunication market in Sudan. Interview was chosen over questionnaire due to limited no of professionals in the area of research.

Sample Selection

The way that the interviewees were selected and the determination of their number have great importance as they might greatly affect the overall results and conclusions of the study.

In order to define the possible interviewees, a selection criteria had been clearly set. All the selected interviewees should comply with these criteria. The interviewees should be familiar with:

- Cooperation Strategies
- Telecom market in Sudan
- Possible cooperation areas in telecom field, mainly the infrastructure sharing issues and its different dimensions.

They should also have knowledge of the way that cooperation in infrastructure sharing decisions are made and strategies are formed by the network operators. The main reason that this criterion had been set is to derive valid information about the strategic considerations of the network operators concerning infrastructure sharing.

Some possible interviewees that fulfill the above mentioned criteria can be employees of a network operator (e.g. Zain, MTN, Sudani or Canar). However, they do not need necessarily to work in companies that provide mobile network services. They can come from other sectors (e.g. universities, consultancy companies, regulatory authorities) given that they meet the selection criteria.

Before interviewing any interviewee, their positions, backgrounds, research interests, areas of involvement and other relevant information were tested thoroughly to be sure that they meet the selection criteria, most of them were proposed by Dr. Elsaddig Saeed (University Professor) and Engineer Mustafa Abdelhafeez the general Director of Technical Affairs in the National Telecommunication Corporation (Telecom Regulator) because they know more about telecom and strategy fields.

The interview questions were sent to them by E- mail or delivered by hand before the interview date, by doing such actions the researcher increased trust and certainty that selected interviewee would be capable of providing valid and valuable information.

Interviewee list has been divided into two sub lists:

List1: Twenty interviewees from telecom operators

List2: Twenty interviewees from universities, regulator and infrastructure owner but not operators.

Interview Design and Question

The interview is divided into two parts, part one is about current situation of implementing cooperation strategies and the drivers and barriers to it, and part two is about how the decisions of cooperation or not are made when implementing strategy. For each group of interviewees different set of questions were prepared, but the main questions of the interview refer to the same concepts. The main concepts were drivers and barriers for cooperation, final decision of cooperation and trade-offs identifications.

The interview was designed to be Semi-structured interview so as leave the door open for discussion and unexplored aspects to appear.

Before conducting the interview, the questions were reviewed by Dr. Badreldin Mirgani, Dr. M.A.H Abbas and Dr. Elsaddig Saeed. Dr. Mirgani is a university professor, strategy expert and he is the supervisor of this study, Dr. Abbas is university professor, telecom consultant and later he became this study co-

supervisor and Dr. Saeed is a university professor specialized in wireless communication and has a deep knowledge in the telecom field.

LTE Joint Investment Analysis using Game Theory

The mobile market is a fast emerging market. In the past years mobile phones changed from devices that can only be used to make calls, to devices with text messaging, GPS, internet access, mobile payments and many more capabilities. Consumers can use these new services because of the fast development of technology for cellular networks. To handle continuously increasing data traffic, which is a result of the extra services, upgrade to better technologies is necessary. Long Term Evolution technology (LTE) is the latest technology in mobile market. Mobile operators have to upgrade their networks to the latest technologies, to handle the increase in data traffic. But the upgrade is costly compared to the profits induced by the increased data volumes⁽¹⁾. This section is studying cooperation strategies among mobile operators as a solution to the problem.

In this way the costs for upgrading the shared network to the new technology will be divided among all operators and operational expenditures will decrease. While Cooperation in building and upgrading networks reduces costs, it also has influence on the possibility to differentiate on Network level.

Mobile operators will be forced to differentiate on other levels, which will bring extra expenses. The decision whether to make a joint investment in LTE technology is therefore non transparent⁽²⁾.

Therefore it would be desirable to get more insights on what might happen. The decision of one mobile operator influences the other operators in the same market. Game theory is a good tool to model situations where competitors have to make strategic decisions and their decisions are influenced by other agents.

¹ 'SAPHYRE Sharing Physical Resources – Mechanisms and Implementations for Wireless Networks' <<http://www.saphyre.eu/>> [accessed 27 May 2014].

² 'SAPHYRE Sharing Physical Resources – Mechanisms and Implementations for Wireless Networks'.

In sections one and two the researcher studied the effect of passive infrastructure sharing as a cooperation strategy between telecommunication companies in Sudan.

In this section the game theory analysis tool will be conducted to study the option of implementing cooperation strategies to upgrade the existing mobile networks to latest technology.

As explained in the literature review game theory with its focus on the interactions of multiple players, each trying to maximize their own rewards, is a natural fit for many types of business issues. It provides a structured way to analyze the set of possible strategies and recommends an optimal strategy for each player.

In Sudan there are three mobile operators competing in the mobile market, the three operators shared the mobile subscribers till the third quarter of the year 2014 as shown by table 3.1

Table 4.1: Data Market Share in Sudan

Operator	Share	Percentage
Zain	4,645,317	45.86%
MTN	3,484,289	34.40%
Sudani	2,000,000	19.74%
Total	10,129,606	100%

Source: National Telecommunication Corporation

When mobile operators share their networks to make a joint investment, this can be seen as a coalition formation of these mobile operators, the questions the researcher is looking to answer are: *Will cooperation in investing and building LTE network between competitors in the mobile market lead to reduction in capital and operation costs?* and *Is the reduction if found attractive for competitors to cooperate?*

A game theory model derived by SAPHYRE^{1*} will be used to study the cooperation case in Sudan if the operators decided to invest in the LTE technology.

Basics of the network sharing game⁽²⁾

In order to implement the network sharing game model developed by SAPHYRE, we have to specify the set of players, the strategies available to each player and the payoff functions, which describes for each player the payoff for every combination of strategies.

The mobile operators are the players in this game. In Sudan there are three mobile operators(MNOs). The complexity of the model increases fast when the number of players increase. Reason for that is the fast increasing number of strategies and outcomes. Therefore, SAPHYRE considered mainly sets of players consisting of 2 or 3 players which is quite enough to our case in Sudan.

To describe the set of strategies we should take several things into account. Each player should have the control over the decision to invest alone or not invest at all. On the other hand, the decision to invest jointly can only be made if one of or two of the joining players agree. Also, a cooperating player should be able to refuse cooperation with another player, if he prefers. So no player can decide to join a cooperation, without permission of the players in the cooperation. The game is therefore an exclusive membership game, as defined in chapter two.

The strategies in the game had been divided into two categories of decisions:

1. Decisions to invest on LTE or not
2. Decisions to propose a joint investment

At first we look at what the outcomes and payoff functions should look like, because this will not depend on the rules of the game. The set of outcomes of the

*Sharing Physical Resources Project, a project aimed to study the effect of resource sharing in mobile market in the European Union conducted by the Strategic Business Analysis Department, Netherlands in 2011

² 'SAPHYRE Sharing Physical Resources – Mechanisms and Implementations for Wireless Networks'.
<<http://www.saphyre.eu/>> [accessed 27 May 2014].

game should include all possible combinations of joint investments combined with separate investments and mobile operators who do not invest.

In a two player game, a market with only two mobile operators, here are the expected outcomes:

1. No MNO invests.
2. MNO 1 invests alone.
3. MNO 2 invests alone.
4. Each MNO invest separately.
5. MNO 1 and MNO 2 invest jointly.

In a three players game, the expected outcomes grow:

1. No MNO invests.
2. MNO 1 invests alone.
3. MNO 2 invests alone.
4. MNO 3 invests alone.
5. MNO 1 and MNO 2 invest separately; MNO 3 doesn't invest.
6. MNO 1 and MNO 3 invest separately; MNO 2 doesn't invest.
7. MNO 2 and MNO 3 invest separately; MNO 1 doesn't invest.
8. All MNOs invest separately.
9. MNO 1 and MNO 2 invest jointly; MNO 3 doesn't invest.
10. MNO 1 and MNO 3 invest jointly; MNO 2 doesn't invest.
11. MNO 2 and MNO 3 invest jointly; MNO 1 doesn't invest.
12. MNO 1 and MNO 2 invest jointly; MNO 3 invests alone.
13. MNO 1 and MNO 3 invest jointly; MNO 2 invests alone.
14. MNO 2 and MNO 3 invest jointly; MNO 1 invests alone.
15. All MNOs invest jointly.

The payoff functions should give a value to each of the outcomes for each MNO. This value should tell what the MNO wins or loses when the market changes to the scenario described by the outcome. To specify this value for each MNO and to each outcome, will be hard. The payoff functions depend on numerous factors

such as the MNOs market position, customer relationship, strategy, resources etc. All these factors should be taken into account when calculating the value of a sharing scenario, while giving a value to the separate factors is already a rough guess. To avoid this valuation process SAPHYRE model defined the payoff function in a different way. If we play a non-cooperative game this is possible. In a non-cooperative game, the objective for each player is to maximize his own payoff; i.e. to get the outcome with the highest value possible.

The value of the outcome tells us two things: which outcome is better, and how much better.

The model excluded the second purpose of the value, so it is possible to forget about the actual values. The only thing we need to know for each two outcomes, is which one is better, but not how much better. So for each player the payoff function is given by an order of preference on the different outcomes. In the two player game the payoff function for MNO1 could look like this:

$$\{2\} > \{5\} > \{4\} > \{1\} > \{3\}$$

MNO1 perceives that he profits the most from the situation where he is the only one that invests in LTE technology, followed by the case where he jointly invests with MNO2 in a network. The third best scenario is when they both invest separately, followed by the scenario where they both make no investment. The least valuable scenario for MNO1 is when MNO2 is the only one who invests. The function only tells that {2} is more valuable than {5}, but not how much more.

By formulating the payoff functions in this way, we can avoid having to determine all values of the outcomes. As a start this is a good way to analyze the different scenarios without assuming too much about the value of outcomes. The model referred to these functions as preference functions.

Non Cooperative Simultaneous Games

The SAPHYRE model has taken into account only the non-cooperative simultaneous game and discarded the sequential game because it is too difficult to consider all the possibilities of the outcomes⁽¹⁾.

A simultaneous non-cooperative game with complete information is called a normal form game. As stated before, the assumptions of a normal form game do not reflect the actual game that is played in practice. In practice MNOs will not make their decisions simultaneously and independently and they do not have enough information about their competitors to know their payoff functions. However, the representation as a normal form game is very useful, because it gives information about the stable outcomes of the game, at least for the independent initial positions of the MNOs. Based on these outcomes MNOs can make decisions about cooperation with other MNOs.⁽²⁾

Two players game⁽³⁾

The two players are represented by player A and B, with strategy sets

$$S_A = \{X, A, AB(X), AB(\Gamma)\}.$$

$$S_B = \{X, B, AB(X), AB(\Gamma)\}.$$

Table 4.2: Different strategies for players in two players simultaneous game

Strategy A	Strategy B	
X	X	Do Nothing
A	B	Invest in the technology alone
AB(X)	AB(X)	Propose a joint investment to the other player, if rejected do nothing
AB(Γ)	AB(Γ)	Propose a joint investment to the other player, if rejected invest alone

Source: <<http://www.saphyre.eu/>> [accessed 27 May 2014].

¹ Fieke Offergelt, 'Cooperation among Competitors' (unpublished Master Thesis, Leiden, 2011), p. 19.

² Christian Julmi, *Introduction to Game Theory* (BookBoon, 2012), p. 35.

³ 'SAPHYRE Sharing Physical Resources – Mechanisms and Implementations for Wireless Networks'.

The first two strategies are decisions whether to make an investment and the last two strategies are decisions to propose a joint investment, as defined before. The combinations of the strategies give the following set of outcomes of the game:

$$U = S_A \times S_B = \{(X,X), (A,X), (X,B), (A,B), (A\&B)\}$$

Table 4.3: Outcome of two player game

Outcome	
(X,X)	They both do nothing
(A,X)	Player A invests and player B does nothing
(X,B)	Player A does nothing and player B invests
(A,B)	Both players invest separately
(A&B)	They jointly invest in the technology

Source: <<http://www.saphyre.eu/>> [accessed 27 May 2014].

Normal form games are represented by matrices, in the network sharing game this will give the following matrix representation:

	X	A	AB(X)	AB(Γ)
X	(X,X)	(A,X)	(X,X)	(A,X)
B	(X,B)	(A,B)	(X,B)	(A,B)
AB(X)	(X,X)	(A,X)	(A&B)	(A&B)
AB(Γ)	(X,B)	(A,B)	(A&B)	(A&B)

Because in our case in Sudan we have three mobile operators we use the same model for the three players game

Three player game

To describe the three player game, we let us call the players A, B and C. We assume that the players are not symmetric. This is a logical assumption, because there are no markets where all MNOs are the same (follow the exact same strategies, have the same resources, have the same amount of funds, etc.). We

rank the MNOs by the amount of funds they can invest in building a new network, so player A is the ‘biggest’ and player C is the ‘smallest’.

Assuming this, will make the formulation of the strategy set and preference functions more straight forward. As a reminder, the sets of available strategies in this game are given by:

$$S_A = \{X, A, AB(X), AC(X), AB(\Gamma), AC(\Gamma), ABC(X), ABC(\Gamma), ABC(\Delta)\}$$

$$S_B = \{X, B, AB(X), BC(X), AB(\Gamma), BC(\Gamma), ABC(X), ABC(\Gamma), ABC(\Delta)\}$$

$$S_C = \{X, C, AC(X), BC(X), AC(\Gamma), BC(\Gamma), ABC(X), ABC(\Gamma), ABC(\Delta)\}$$

Table 4.4: Different Strategies for three players game

S_A	S_B	S_C	
X	X	X	Do not invest
A	B	C	Invest in the technology alone
$AB(X)$	$AB(X)$	$AC(X)$	Propose a joint investment to the biggest player, else do not invest
$AC(X)$	$BC(X)$	$BC(X)$	Propose a joint investment to the smallest player, else do not invest
$AB(\Gamma)$	$AB(\Gamma)$	$AC(\Gamma)$	Propose a joint investment to the biggest player, else invest alone
$AC(\Gamma)$	$BC(\Gamma)$	$BC(\Gamma)$	Propose a joint investment to the smallest player, else invest alone
$ABC(X)$	$ABC(X)$	$ABC(X)$	Propose a joint investment to both other players, else do not invest
$ABC(\Gamma)$	$ABC(\Gamma)$	$ABC(\Gamma)$	Propose a joint investment to both other players, else invest alone
$ABC(\Delta)$	$ABC(\Delta)$	$ABC(\Delta)$	Propose a joint investment to both other players, else invest with all players who made the same proposal.

Source: Source: <<http://www.saphyre.eu/>> [accessed 27 May 2014].

As stated before, the combination of these strategies leads to fifteen different outcomes.

$$U = S_A \times S_B \times S_C = \{(X, X, X), (A, X, X), (X, B, X), (X, X, C), (A, B, X), (A, X, C), (X, B, C), (A, B, C), (A\&B, X), (A\&C, X), (B\&C, X), (A\&C, B), (B\&C, A), (A\&B\&C)\}$$

Table 4.5: Different outcomes in the three player game

Outcome	
(X,X,X)	All three do not invest
(A,X,X)	Player A invests, B and C do not invest
(X,B,X)	Player B invests, A and C do not invest
(X,X,C)	Player C invests, A and B do not invest
(A,B,X)	Player A and B invest separately, C does not invest
(A,X,C)	Player A and C invest separately, B does not invest
(X,B,C)	Player B and C invest separately, A does not invest
(A,B,C)	All three players invest separately
(A&B,X)	Player A and B invest jointly, C does not invest
(A&C,X)	Player A and C invest jointly, B does not invest
(B&C,X)	Player B and C invest jointly, A does not invest
(A&B,C)	Player A and B invest jointly, C invests alone
(A&C,B)	Player A and C invest jointly, B invests alone
(B&C,A)	Player B and C invest jointly, A invests alone
(A&B&C)	All three players invest jointly

Source: researcher

Each outcome has a different value for each player, given by the payoff functions p_A, p_B, p_C . These have to be defined for each player. As before, these functions give a preference order on the possible outcome of the game. Because there are 15 possible outcomes, every player can have 15 different preference functions. It would be impossible to test all functions.

Moreover, this wouldn't be very interesting, because most of these preference functions do not describe a realistic situation. In order to describe realistic situations, we assume that the following has to hold.

Because of the assumption that the new technology gives a competitive advantage to the investors, a player doesn't prefer the situation where the competitor (jointly or separately) invests in LTE technology, while he does not. For example, the situation where player A prefers (B&C, X) over (B&C, A) does not occur.

Less competition is always better; therefore, all players will prefer the situation where the smallest number of competitors invest. The players also prefer competition from weak over strong competitors. So for players the order (A, X, X) > (A, X, C) > (A, B, X) > (A, B, C) has to be respected, as well as the orders: (A&B,X) > (A&B,C)

and (A&C,X) > (A&C,B)

Modeling the Sudanese Market

The SAPHYRE model mentioned in this section will be used to model the Sudanese mobile market. To use this model, we will need to know the preference functions for Zain, MTN and Sudani.

In order to determine these, we will estimate the value of all different coalition structures in this market for each MNO. There are different factors that influence the value of a structure. We measure this influence by means of costs.

The preference functions can be used to draw conclusions about the coalitional structure that will most likely be formed. The model will be used to calculate which coalitional structures are equilibria. Based on the set of equilibria can be argued which coalitional structure will most likely be the result in the Sudanese market.

The modeling will be done in Khartoum state, reasons behind that

1. It is too difficult to get the coverage data for all Sudan
2. Most of mobile subscribers are concentrated at Khartoum.

The modeling will be done with the following assumptions

1. market share has a uniform distribution all over Sudan, so we can implement the market share data to the Khartoum case.
2. Population in Khartoum has a uniform distribution, so when calculating the number of sites needed we can distribute it easily.
3. The frequency will be used is 1800 MHz
4. All MNOs want full coverage in Khartoum.
5. All different parties will try to maintain serving the same market share with LTE technology, as they serve now.

Chapter 5

Research Results

Cooperation real situation

Site Survey

The following tables shows the data collected in the first day from Khartoum to Atbara about 350 kilometers and the data collected in the second day of the trip from Atbara to Port Sudan around 460 kilometers

Table 5.1: Survey data Khartoum Atbara

Khartoum Atbara High Way Coverage					
ID	Area	Number of Towers	Distance between towers in Km	Distance from Previous Tower	Power source
1	Abuhaleema	2	0.2	National Grid
2	khogalab	1	...	0.8	National Grid
3	kabashi	1	12	National Grid
4	kabashi	1	1.2	National Grid
5	Kabashi	3	0.2	1.5	National Grid
6	Algili east	1	7	National Grid
7	Algaili west	6	0.5	0.6	National Grid
8	Garri	1	17	National Grid
9	Free Zone	2	0.2	2	National Grid
10	kilo 32	2	0.5	14	National Grid
11	kilo 39	1	7	National Grid
12	kilo 50	1	11	National Grid
13	kilo 51	2	0.3	1	National Grid
14	kilo 58	1	7	National Grid
15	kilo 65	1	7	National Grid
16	kilo 82	1	17	National Grid
17	kilo 88	2	0.5	6	National Grid
18	kilo 92	2	0.02	4	National Grid
19	kilo 128	1	36	National Grid
20	kilo 129	2	0.2	1	National Grid
21	(shendi)	6	0.5	2	National Grid
22	kilo 158	1	13	National Grid
23	(kaboshia)	2	0.2	13	National Grid
24	(al3agaba)	2	0.005	19	National Grid
25	kilo 194	2	0.1	4	National Grid
26	Atbara	1		49	National Grid

Source: Researcher

Table 5.2 a: Atbara Port Sudan

Atbara Port Sudan High Way Coverage					
ID	Area	Number of Towers	Distance between adjacent towers km	Distance from previous Tower	Power Type
1	Kilo 32	1	GenSet
2	kilo 35	1	3	Solar
3	kilo 53	2	0.6	18	GenSet + Solar
4	kilo 69	1	16	GenSet
5	kilo 70	1	1.5	Solar
6	kilo 89	1	18.5	GenSet
7	kilo 91	1	2	Solar
8	kilo 103	1	12	GenSet
9	kilo 104	1	1	Solar
10	kilo 109	1	4.5	GenSet
11	kilo120	1	11	Solar
12	kilo 134	1	14	Solar
13	kilo 139	1	5	GenSet
14	kilo 140	1	1.2	GenSet
15	kilo 150	1	9.6	Solar
16	kilo 164	1	14.2	Solar
17	kilo 170	2	0.15	6	GenSet
18	kilo 173	1	2.8	GenSet
19	kilo 182	1	9.2	Solar
20	kilo 187	2	0.1	5.4	GenSet
21	kilo 195	2	0.05	8	GenSet
22	kilo 196	1	1	GenSet
23	kilo 211	1	15	Solar
24	kilo 224	1	13	Solar
25	kilo 226	2	0.1	2	GenSet
26	kilo 243	3	0.5	17	GenSet

Source: Researcher

Table 5.2 b: Atbara Port Sudan

Atbara Port Sudan High Way Coverage					
ID	Area	Number of Towers	Distance between adjacent towers km	Distance from previous Tower	Power Type
27	kilo 252	2	9.5	GenSet
28	kilo 255	2	0.02	2.5	Solar
29	kilo 263	1	8	GenSet
30	kilo 266	1	2.5	Solar
31	kilo 270	1	4.8	GenSet
32	kilo 281	2	0.05	10.3	GenSet
33	kilo 282	2	0.3	0.6	GenSet
34	kilo 298	1	16.4	GenSet
35	kilo 301	2	0.4	3.7	GenSet
36	kilo 314	1	13	GenSet + Solar
37	kilo 321	2	0.5	7.2	Solar
38	kilo 325	1	3.8	GenSet
39	kilo 338	1	12	GenSet
40	kilo 339	1	1	Solar
41	kilom 250	1	13	GenSet
42	kio 357	2	0.3	5	GenSet
43	kilo 367	3	0.5	10	National Grid
44	kilo 375	1	8.2	GenSet
45	kilo 389	1	2	GenSet
46	kilo 403	1	4	GenSet
47	kilo 405	1	2	Solar
48	kilo 411	1	6	GenSet
49	kilo 422	2	0.1	11.4	GenSet + Solar
50	kilo 439	2	0.2	16.6	GenSet
51	kilo 442	1	2.6	GenSet
52	kilo 459	2	0.05	17.4	GenSet

Source: Researcher

Following are some photos taken during the highway site survey and they show that some sites are built without any degree of cooperation between telecom operator, in some areas the distance between the sites was only 5 meters.

Figure 5.1: Examples of lack of cooperation

For Atbara city data collected is a little bit different from highway data because inside city tower type can affect the possibility of cooperation, in Atbara each tower has been given an index number and the number of antenna sets also considered.

The following table shows the data collected from the city.

Table 5.3a: Survey data collected in Atbara City

Atbara City Coverage					
ID	Area	Tower Type	No of Antennas	Adjacent Towers	Adjacent Tower ID
1	Airport	GT	1	none
2	Hai Almatar	GT	3	1	3,5,6
3	Hai Almatar	GT	2	3	2,5,6
4	Shaabia	GT	3	none
5	Hai Almatar	RT	2	3	2,3,6
6	Hai Almatar	GT	1	3	2,3,5
7	khilewa	GT	1	none
8	khilewa	GT	2	none
9	khilewa	GT	1	2	10,11
10	khilewa	GT	2	2	9,11
11	khilewa	GT	1	2	9,10
12	alshamali	GT	1	none
13	Alsayala	GT	2	2	14,15
14	Alsayala	GT	1	2	13,15
15	Kahraba	GT	1	2	13,14
16	Alsayala	GT	1	2	17,18
17	Alsayala	GT	1	2	16,18
18	Alsayala	GT	1	2	16,17
19	Alsayala	GT	2	none
20	Dakhla	GT	1	none
21	Ombakol	GT	1	1	22
22	Ombakol	GT	1	1	21
23	Ombakol	GT	1	none
24	Market	RT	1	3	25,26,27
25	Market	RT	2	3	24,26,27

Source: Researcher

Table 5.3b: Survey data collected in Atbara City

Atbara City Coverage					
ID	Area	Tower Type	No of Antennas	Adjacent Towers	Adjacent Tower ID
26	Post office	GT	3	3	24,25,27
27	Mrafiq	GT	3	3	24,25,26
28	Mawraa	GT	1	none
29	Murabaat	GT	1	1	30
30	Taxation	GT	2	1	29
31	Puplic Yard	GT	3	1	32
32	Maashat	GT	2	1	31
33	Fakimadani	GT	2	2	34,35
34	Itihad Club	GT	2	2	33,35
35	Itihad Club	GT	1	2	33,34
36	Sharqi	GT	2	none
37	Sharqi	GT	2	1	38
38	Sharqi	GT	1	1	37
39	Sharqi	GT	2	none
40	Wihda	GT	2	1	41
41	Wihda	GT	1	1	40
42	Sharqi	GT	2	none
43	Shaabia	GT	2	none
44	Real State Bank	GT	1	1	45
45	Real State Bank	GT	1	1	44
46	Mugran	GT	1	none
47	Mugran	GT	2	none
48	Mugran	GT	2	none
49	Mugran	GT	1	none
50	Mugran	GT	1	none
51	Mugran	GT	1	none

Source: Researcher

Analysis

Data collected from this survey has been analyzed and the results are shown in following tables:

Table 5.4: Khartoum Atbara Cooperation Data

Area	Number of Towers	Distance between adjacent towers km
Abuhaleema	2	0.2
Kabashi entrance from North	3	0.2
Free Zone	2	0.2
kilo 92	2	0.02
kilo 129	2	0.2
kilo171 (kaboshia)	2	0.2
kilo 190 (al3agaba)	2	0.005
kilo 194	2	0.1

Source: Researcher

Table 5.5: Atbara City Cooperation Data

ID	Area	Tower Type	No of Antennas	Adjacent Towers
3	Hai Almatar	GT	2	3
6	Hai Almatar	GT	1	3
9	khilewa	GT	1	2
10	khilewa	GT	2	2
11	khilewa	GT	1	2
13	Alsayala	GT	2	2
14	Alsayala	GT	1	2
15	Kahraba	GT	1	2
16	Alsayala	GT	1	2
17	Alsayala	GT	1	2
18	Alsayala	GT	1	2
21	Ombakol	GT	1	1
22	Ombakol	GT	1	1
29	Murabaat	GT	1	1
30	Taxation	GT	2	1
32	Maashat	GT	2	1
33	Fakimadani	GT	2	2
34	Itihad Club	GT	2	2
35	Itihad Club	GT	1	2
37	Sharqi	GT	2	1
38	Sharqi	GT	1	1
40	Wihda	GT	2	1
41	Wihda	GT	1	1
44	Real State Bank	GT	1	1
45	Real State Bank	GT	1	1

Source: Researcher

Table 5.6: Atbara Port Sudan Cooperation Data

ID	Area	Number of Towers	Distance between adjacent towers km
17	kilo 170	2	0.15
20	kilo 187	2	0.1
21	kilo 195	2	0.05
25	kilo 226	2	0.1
27	kilo 252	2	0.2
28	kilo 255	2	0.02
32	kilo 281	2	0.05
49	kilo 422	2	0.1
50	kilo 439	2	0.2
52	kilo 459	2	0.05

Source: Researcher

The above tables show sites built in one area within a distance where it was technically possible to use one tower for more than one company but each company constructed its own site including yard, room, power supply, tower and cooling system.

For Khartoum – Atbara section the number of sites where it was possible to implement cooperation were 17 sites out of 49 which is almost 35% of the sites.

There were also 14 sites where it was possible technically to implement cooperation with some modification in the design which is almost 28% of the total sites.

For Atbara - Port Sudan section the number of sites where it was possible to implement cooperation were 10 sites out of 52 which is almost 19% of the total sites.

Inside Atbara city the number of sites where it was possible to implement cooperation were 25 sites out of 51 which is almost 50% of the total sites.

For the whole highway the number of sites where it was possible to implement cooperation were 29 sites out of 101 which is almost 29% of the total sites in

addition to 14 sites where it possible to implement cooperation with some technical modification the total number of sites will reach 43 and the percentage will increase to 43%.

Real Cooperation Cases

In this part real cases of implementing company's strategies are shown, in the first case cooperation is established between a telecom operator (MTN) and the Sudanese Electricity Transmission company (SETCO), SETCO is not a telecom operator but it operators a private telecom network owned by the ministry of Electricity and irrigation used for operation of electricity network and energy sale. SETCO covers almost all Sudan by its private fiber network with a total length of about 5000 kilometers, while MTN had no license to own a fiber network, its license is limited to offer mobile services.

MTN was planning to link the international gateway in Port Sudan to Khartoum with a total length of approximately 800 kilometers and to link its stations in Shendi, Atbara and Port Sudan cities by the same link. If MTN tried to build its own fiber it should ask for a license from the regulator and this has a valuable cost and takes time, and if they had the license it will take a long time to bid, evaluate and implement the project.

MTN and SETCO signed an agreement that allows MTN to use a single pair of fibers to link the desired locations, in addition to the fiber the agreement allowed MTN to co-locate its equipment in SETCO stations, by signing this agreement MTN saved around two years of project implementation time, started to get revenues quickly and saved a huge amount of the budget dedicated to the project.

Although Zain network was big and covers almost all western states, but it was isolated from other country's parts and it seemed to be useless,

Canar was thinking to reach areas which Zain reached but it was also difficult to do for many reasons such as finance, civil war started in those areas and also it needs many years to complete such a big project.

Both companies signed a commercial agreement allows each one to use the others fiber network, by signing this agreement both were happy, Zain at last linked its isolated island with the capital Khartoum and Canar now has access to the whole western states. After this agreement Zain saved the Capex that was reserved to buy, dig, and lay about 610 kilometers of fiber, and Canar also saved the Capex needed for about 800 kilometers of fibers.

Figure 5.3: Zain and Canar Fiber Networks after Cooperation

Source: Researcher

Interview

Interview Results

Questions 1,2,3,4 and 15 in the operator’s interview are direct questions and can be evaluated without need to additional analysis because they are concerning in the current level of cooperation and the willingness of top management to cooperate, these question had been asked only to decision maker in the telecom operators.

Table 5.7: Answers of the interview question 1

Does the company that you work for apply any cooperation strategies with others?					
Answer	Total	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	4	4	100%	0	0%

Table 5.8: Answers of the interview question 2

If your answer for question (1) is yes, please explain what the most commonly adopted infrastructure sharing categories are and what types of alliances that were adopted.				
Answer	sharing type	Total Answers	Frequency	Percentage
Answer 1	Site Sharing	4	3	75%
Answer 2	Tower Sharing	4	3	75%
Answer 3	Dark Fiber sharing	4	2	50%

Table 5.9: Answers of the interview question 3

Is your company willing to cooperate with other companies to jointly build infrastructure?					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	4	4	100%	0	0%

With whom you are willing to cooperate?

Competitor :4
 New Entrant :0
 Both :2

Table 5.10: Answers of the interview question 4

Is your company willing to cooperate in swap fibre roots with other utilities?					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	4	4	100%	0	0%

With whom You are willing to cooperate?

Competitor 2
 New Entrant 0
 Other 4

Findings in questions 1,2,3 and 4

From the answers given by telecom operators we can conclude that all operators are applying some kinds of cooperation in implementing their strategy of network expansions, but they limited their cooperation only in sharing existing sites, towers and fiber cables. There is no any joint venture agreed between companies to cooperate in building new infrastructure, but they are willing to cooperate in building infrastructure in the future, all operators prefer to cooperate with competitor because competitors are familiar with regulations, equipment, maintenance and the all sharing environment.

For the fiber swapping they are all prefer to cooperate mostly with infrastructure owners (non-competitors), two operators are willing to cooperate with competitors and the other two are not because they think this will lead them to lose a competitive advantage in the future. Also all companies did not mention the option of cooperation with new entrant, because they think that new entrant

normally starts with new technologies and if they help them they start delivering services faster and this may affect their competitive advantages.

Table 5.11: Answers of the interview question 5

Operator Question	What do you consider to be the main drivers for your company to cooperate in infrastructure (Active and Passive) with other utilities?
Others Question	From your point of view ,What do you consider to be the main drivers for a network operator to cooperate in infrastructure (Active and Passive) with other utilities?

Table 5.12: Answers of the interview question 9

Operator Question	What do you consider to be the main barriers for your company to cooperate in infrastructure (Active and Passive) with other utilities?
Others Question	From your point of view ,What do you consider to be the main barriers for a network operator to cooperate in infrastructure (Active and Passive) with other utilities?

These question had been asked to the both lists, some answers had been given directly from the interviewees, the researcher named these answers (direct answers), if the interviewee not mentioned one of the drivers or barriers already stated in the literature review then the interviewer will ask about it and if the answer is yes it will be recorded and named as (proposed answer), frequencies and percentage of the answer to the whole sample are calculated and plotted using excel charts and the two variable were used to prioritize drivers and barriers accordingly.

Table 5.13: Answers of the interview question (5) – Drivers of Cooperation

No	Driver	Sample Volume	Direct Answer	proposed Answer	Not Mentioned
1	Cost Reduction	40	40	0	0
2	New Revenue Stream	40	20	4	16
3	Strategic Purpose	40	2	0	38
4	Regulator Policies	40	14	10	16
5	Enhance Network easier	40	7	12	21
6	Ease of maintenance	40	10	9	21
7	Reduce Service Cost	40	22	10	8
8	enhance Competition	40	25	8	7
9	New services and better QoS	40	40	0	0
10	Share the risk among more than one operator	40	32	7	1
11	reduce expansion time/fast deployment of new systems	40	40	0	0
12	Increase capacity in congested area	40	30	7	3
13	cover new areas easy	40	40	0	0
14	lack of sites	40	10	9	21
15	win - win	40	2	0	38
16	Reduce environmental hazards	40	28	10	2

Figure 5.4: Answers of the interview question (5) – Drivers of Cooperation

Findings in question 5

The main drivers found for cooperation were Cost Reduction, introducing new services and better Quality of Service (QoS), reduce expansion time/fast deployment of new systems, cover new areas easy, reduce environmental hazards and Share the risk among more than one operator, regulator policies had a frequency score of 60% but most interviewees agreed that although there are policies for cooperation but they are not active.

Table 5.14: Answers of the interview question (9) – Barriers of Cooperation

No	Driver	Sample Volume	Direct Answer	proposed Answer	Not Mentioned
1	long term loss of competition advantage	40	25	9	6
2	Type of antenna	40	18	12	10
3	Radiation hazard (Site owner)	40	7	12	21
4	cooperation with competitor	40	24	8	8
5	Coverage is a competitive advantage	40	7	11	22
6	High leasing prices	40	10	7	23
7	lack of regulation	40	21	13	6
8	Future expansion	40	11	8	21
9	Lack of trust	40	24	7	9
10	Hosting contracts not allow additional equipment	40	4	10	26
11	Mast design	40	6	10	24

Figure 5.5: Answers of the interview question (9) – Barriers of Cooperation

Source: Researcher

Findings in question 9

The main barriers found for cooperation were long term loss of competition advantage and lack of regulation with a percentage of 85% of the total list, all interviewees think that the two barriers are linked together, if regulation became better and governed the telecom market correctly, then the fears of losing competitive advantage will be minimized, these barriers are followed by cooperation with competitor, lack of trust, type of antenna and mast design, still the concept of cooperating with competitors is not known and really competitors are forcing it, also most of operators do not trust each other in addition to that the existing sites had been designed for the current use only so some masts are not deigned to carry additional load, also some companies are using different antennas for different technologies for that 3 antennas may be hanged in one tower to be used by only one company, the new types of antennas support different technologies , hence one antenna is enough.

Questions 6,7,8 and 10

Question 6,7 and 10 examines the willingness of the operators to cooperate in infrastructure sharing either by providing, leasing or building together also examines areas where operators are more willing to cooperate, while question 8 examines their willingness to lease from infrastructure owners (non-competitors).

Table 5.15: Answers of the interview question 6

Operator Question	At which stage your company will be more willing to provide infrastructure for sharing?
Others Question	When do you think is a network operator more willing to provide his infrastructure for sharing?

At the beginning of the network deployment	:0
As the network matures	:29
In both phases	:6
In none phase	:5

Table 5.16: Answers of the interview question (7)

Operator Question	From your point of view, where are you willing to cooperate in sharing or building infrastructure?
Others Question	From your point of view , Where do you think operators are willing to cooperate in sharing or building infrastructure?

Source: Researcher

Urban areas	:32
Sub urban areas	:7
Rural areas	:15

Table 5.17: Answers of the interview question (8)

Operator Question	Will your company be willing to lease from infrastructure owners (non- mobile operators)		
Others Question	Do you think that operators will be willing to lease from infrastructure owners (non- mobile operators)?		
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	No
Frequency	4	4	0

Table 5.18: Answers of the interview question (10)

Operator Question	When is your company less willing to allow infrastructure sharing?
Others Question	When do you think is a network operator less willing to allow sharing of his infrastructure?

At the beginning of the network :27
 As the network matures :13

Findings on questions 6,7,8, and 10

From the answers of the questions it is clear that all operators are really willing to cooperate with infrastructure owners that are not competitors. For the willingness of cooperation with other operator most of answers showed that operators are likely willing to cooperate after the maturity of their networks and they are less willing to cooperate at the beginning of network deployment except in rural areas where most of the comments stated that it is better to coordinate from beginning.

Also we found that operators are willing to cooperate in Urban and Rural areas more than suburban areas, they justified this willingness because in urban areas it is very difficult and costly to find a site and rural areas they prefer it to reduce the cost.

Table 5.19: Answers of the interview question (11)

Do you think that infrastructure sharing will affect competition?					
Answer	Total	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	40	40	100%	0	0%

Finding of question 11

All interviewees agreed that infrastructure sharing will affect the competition and stated that it is positive affect because it will to balance the market, 6 answers stated that the affect will be negative and justified their answer because of the lack of regulation that govern competition.

Questions 14 and 15

These question examines to which degree of infrastructure sharing operators can cooperate, question 14 examines the passive sharing while 15 examines the active sharing.

Table 5.20: Answers of the interview question (14)

Operator Question	Up to which sharing category are you willing to cooperate in infrastructure?
Others Question	Up to which sharing category do you think is a network operator willing to adopt-provide infrastructure?

Site Sharing 40

Dark fiber and Transmission 32

Table 5.21: Answers of the interview question (15)

For the 4th generation network, are you willing to jointly invest in building the network?					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	4	0	0%	4	100%

Findings on questions 14 and 15

From answers we can conclude that operators are interested only on site sharing and to some extent the fiber and transmission. There is no any interest in active sharing

Questions 12 and 13

Table 5.22: Answers of the interview question (12)

Operator Question	How is decision making done in your company concerning cooperation? Is the final choice for Cooperation a matter of trade-offs or are there other considerations that drive your company's choices? Can you please explain?
Others Question	How do you think is decision making done by a network operator concerning cooperation? Is the final choice for cooperation a matter of trade-offs or are there other considerations that drive his choices? Can you please explain?

Answer:

Tradeoffs :35

Other :5

Table 5.23: Interview question (13)

Operator Question	What is the most important trade-off that determines your company's choices regarding to cooperation in sharing or jointly building infrastructure? From the identified trade-offs are both variables of equal importance or is any of them of higher importance and if yes which?
Others Question	Which do you think is the most important trade-off that determines a network operator's choices regarding cooperation? From the identified trade-offs are both variables of equal importance or is any of them of higher importance and if yes which?

Table 5.24: Answers of the interview question (13) – Cooperation Decision Making trade-offs

No	Trade-Off	Sample Volume	Direct Answer	proposed Answer	Not Mentioned	Direct Answer %	Proposed Answer %	Not Mentioned %
1	Retail against Whole Sale	40	25	8	7	62.5	20	17.5
2	Cost against Cooperation	40	31	9	0	77.5	22.5	0
3	Saving time against Building own infrastructure	40	27	8	5	67.5	20	12.5

Figure 5.6: Answers of the interview question (13) answers – Cooperation Decision Making trade-offs

Findings on questions 12 and 13

For the infrastructure receiver and provider, the trade-off of Cost against Cooperation is most important one, operators think a lot before taking the decision of cooperation with competitor, for infrastructure provider the second important trade-off is Retail against Whole Sale while for receiver the second one is Saving time against Building own infrastructure.

There were some trade-offs mentioned by some interviewees but they did not have high frequencies, these trade-offs had been justified by them. The trade-offs are Additional revenue source against helping competition to develop, Costs

against revenues, Costs against service differentiation and Costs against dependent on other operators.

In addition to the trade-offs chosen by the interviewees part of them (35%) linked the decision to case studies, they stated that business cases are much important in decision making.

Questions 16 to 21

Table 5.25: Answers of the interview question (16)

Do you think that encouraging infrastructure sharing might help companies extend their networks further into rural and remote areas / hard to reach?					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	20	20	100%	0	0%

Table 5.26: Answers of the interview question (17)

Do you agree that the ability to share other companies' infrastructure would reduce the costs of network expansion?					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	20	20	100%	0	0%

Table 5.27: Answers of the interview question (18)

Do you agree that Cooperation with other utilities has helped your company in reducing the Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and operation Expenditure (OPEX)?					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	20	20	100%	0	0%

Table 5.28: Answers of the interview question (19)

The Cooperation has helped your company improve on its service delivery through introduction of value added services(or introduction of innovative product) by means of using capital saved ?					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	20	13	65%	7	35%

Table 5.29: Answers of the interview question (20)

Do you think that Cooperation in infrastructure sharing with other utilities will help your company in reducing the time needed to build or expand infrastructure					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	20	20	100%	0	0%

Table 5.30: Answers of the interview question (21)

Do you think that Cooperation in infrastructure sharing with other utilities will help your company in reducing the effect on environment?					
Answer	Total Answers	Yes	Yes%	No	No %
Frequency	20	20	100%	0	0%

Findings on Question 16 to 21

All interviewees agreed that cooperation in infrastructure building will lead to:

- Help companies extend their networks further into rural and remote areas / hard to reach.
- Reduce the costs of network expansion.
- Reduce the Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and operation Expenditure (OPEX).
- Reduce the time needed to build or expand infrastructure
- Reduce the effect on environment.

For question 19 they suggest that it could help company improve on its service delivery through introduction of value added services (or introduction of innovative product) by means of using capital saved, only when the cooperation level increases, but now the saving would not be that much.

LTE Joint Investment Analysis using Game Theory

Investment in Long Term Evolution technology

The cost of network upgrade to LTE is calculated by site, this cost has been estimated from two vendor's data and consulting experts in telecommunication field to be 85000 dollars per site.

To cover the targeted area by mobile services the sites normally designed to serve 40% of the population at the same time, the sites that are planned to serve this percentage are called Coverage sites. In cases where more than 40% of the population in Khartoum are willing to use the mobile services a need for extra sites that serve the additional subscribers is present, such sites should be ready any time and should be invested within the same time as coverage sites. These sites are called Capacity sites.

Because of the assumption that all MNOs want full coverage in Khartoum , the number of coverage sites is independent of the percentage of the market that an MNO has to serve. Even if an MNO only serves 10% of the market, it still needs all coverage sites.

To serve Khartoum state with LTE technology 200 coverage sites and 300 capacity sites are needed. Using coverage data and the market share data an estimation of the number sites that are necessary for all coalitions done and shown in table (5.31)

Table 5.31: LTE Network Necessary Sites

Company	Coverage	Capacity	Total
Zain (Z)	200	138	338
MTN(M)	200	104	304
Sudani(S)	200	60	260
Zain (Z) & MTN (M)	200	241	441
Zain (Z) & Sudani (S)	200	197	397
Sudani (S) & MTN (M)	200	163	363
Zain (Z),Sudani (S) & MTN (M)	200	300	500

With the estimation of 85000 dollar per site the LTE investment costs for each coalition are calculated. From these values we can already conclude that investment costs will decrease a lot when MNOs cooperate.

Table 5.32: Coalition cost

Coalition	LTE Cost
Z	28,730,000.00
M	25,840,000.00
S	22,100,000.00
Z,M	37,485,000.00
Z,S	33,745,000.00
M,S	30,855,000.00
Z,M,S	42,500,000.00

Saving for each MNO for different Coalitions

The saving for each MNO for the different Coalitions is calculated and showed in table (5.33)

Table 5.33: Saving for different Coalitions

Zain Saving for Different Coalitions						
Coalition	Total Cost	Coverage Cost	Capacity Cost	Zain Share	Saving	Saving Percentage
Z	28,730,000	17,000,000	11,730,000	28,730,000	0	0.00%
Z,M	37,485,000	17,000,000	20,485,000	20,204,985	8,525,015	29.67%
Z,S	33,745,000	17,000,000	16,745,000	20,206,184	8,523,816	29.67%
Z,M,S	42,500,000	17,000,000	25,500,000	17,360,967	11,369,033	39.57%

MTN Saving for Different Coalitions						
Coalition	Total Cost	Coverage Cost	Capacity Cost	MTN Share	Saving	Saving Percentage
M	25,840,000	17,000,000	8,840,000	25,840,000	0	0.00%
Z,M	37,485,000	17,000,000	20,485,000	17,280,015	8,559,985	33.13%
M,S	30,855,000	17,000,000	13,855,000	17,303,325	8,536,675	33.04%
Z,M,S	42,500,000	17,000,000	25,500,000	14,438,667	11,401,333	44.12%

Sudani Saving for Different Coalitions						
Coalition	Total Cost	Coverage Cost	Capacity Cost	Sudani Share	Saving	Saving Percentage
S	22,100,000	17,000,000	5,100,000	22,100,000	0	0.00%
Z,S	33,745,000	17,000,000	16,745,000	13,538,816	8,561,184	38.74%
M,S	30,855,000	17,000,000	13,855,000	13,551,675	8,548,325	38.68%
Z,M,S	42,500,000	17,000,000	25,500,000	10,700,367	11,399,633	51.58%

From these results we can conclude that cooperation will help a lot in saving capital expenditure for all market players specially for the smallest one. Bigger player or the market leader (Zain) will save less compared with operators, it can save from about 30% when invests with one competitor up to 40% when all operators cooperate.

The second player (MTN) can make saving when investing with all operators (44.12%) and when investing with one competitor (33%).

The smallest operator can save a lot when investing with all operators (51.58%) and also can save good value when joint investing with one competitor (around 39%).

As general operators when cooperates in building their network will save capex approximately from 30 up to 52%

Results

Real Cooperation Situation

Cooperation in Sites

From the site survey results and data collected from telecom operators and the National Telecommunication Corporation the researcher found that the cooperation in building new sites or sharing existing ones is very low: 3% for Zain, 0.5% for MTN and unknown situation in Sudatel, for Sudatel the researcher could only count the six (6) sites shared with the Sudanese Electricity Transmission Company (SETCO), this low percentage of cooperation did not match the availability of cooperation that found from the survey which can reach 43% and 50% in medium cities and highways respectively.

From data collected from operation and maintenance managers and planning managers in some telecom companies we can conclude that the cooperation can result in deducting the OPEX and CAPEX as follows:

OPEX savings

- Site rent from 25 to 40 percent depending on the number of cooperating companies.
- Fuel cost from 45 to 60 percent depending on the number of cooperating companies, the addition equipment load will not lead to extra fuel use because generally telecom companies uses high duty generator set with high generation power.
- Guard fees from 40 to 60 percent.

CAPEX savings

- Power and cooling systems from 20 to 40 percent
- Civil work (buildings and tower) from 30 to 60 percent
- Generator sets from 50 to 65 percent

Cooperation in laying fiber roots

The laid fiber optic roots in Sudan are approximately 18,629 kilometers owned by telecom companies and some governmental utilities like electricity and gas, Sudatel owns 32% of the whole fibers while the remaining is owned by others as: Electricity 27%, Canar 15%, Zain 13% and ministry of oil 13%.

Zain – Canar Cooperation

Zain and Canar saved the cost and time of laying fiber cables by signing the commercial agreement, Zain saved the cost and time of laying about 610 kilometers from Khartoum to Elobied, while Canar saved the cost and time for laying fibers from Elobied to Nyala with a total length of approximately 800 kilometers.

According to the prices collected from some telecom experts and telecom vendors, the fiber cable laying approximately cost around 15000 USD per kilometer in the area of cooperation including erection work, by simple calculation we can observe that Canar and Zain had saved more than 21 million dollars (21,180,000 USD) by signing this agreement as CAPEX in addition to the fast enrollment of their services.

Another operator (MTN) also get benefit from this agreement by leasing lit fibers from Canar, MTN used to cover its sites with fiber up to Elobied, but after the agreement they reached Nyala.

MTN – SETCO Cooperation

In the second example MTN saved its CAPEX and time needed to lay an 800 kilometers of fiber cable from Khartoum to Port Sudan by using a single pair of fibers from SETCO's owned fiber.

Applying the same simple calculation used for Zain – Canar Example but with different fiber cable laying approximately cost due to the different area (some areas are rocky) , the average cost is around 18000 USD we can conclude that MTN saved more than 14 million dollars (14,400,000 USD) plus a two years

erection time. MTN OPEX also reduced because fiber rent is cheaper than capacity rent, other telecom operators did not offer MTN dark fiber before. By using SETCO's fiber optic MTN saved CAPEX, OPEX, Time and had full control on its private equipment, while SETCO added a new revenue source.

Figure 5.7: Saving in foreign reserve in fiber laying cooperation

Cooperation Drivers and Barriers

From the interview results the researcher found that the main drivers for using cooperation strategies are:

- Cost Reduction.
- New Revenue Stream.
- Regulator Policies.
- Enhance Network easier.
- Ease of maintenance.
- Reduce Service Cost.
- Enhance Competition.
- New services and better QoS.
- Share the risk among more than one operator.
- Reduce expansion time/fast deployment of new systems/ cover new areas easy.

- Increase capacity in congested area
- lack of sites.
- Reduce environmental hazards.

While the barriers of applying cooperation strategies are:

- Long term loss of competition advantage
- Type of antenna
- Radiation hazard (Site owner)
- Cooperation with competitor
- Coverage is a competitive advantage
- High leasing prices
- Lack of regulation
- Future expansion
- Lack of trust
- Hosting contracts not allow additional equipment
- Mast design

Cooperation decision making

Most of the interviewees stated that the final choices of cooperation in building, providing and receiving infrastructure are taken by considering different trade-offs and business cases results. Some of our them argued that cooperation decisions are actually more strategic decisions.

The most important trade-offs that found are:

- Cost against Cooperation
- Costs against revenues
- Saving time against Building own infrastructure
- Retail against Whole Sale
- Additional revenue source against helping competition to develop
- Costs against service differentiation
- Costs against dependent on other operators

Factors affecting Cooperation decision

From the interview answers there are some factors found that affect the cooperation decision making, these factors are:

- *Area of cooperation* such as; Urban, Suburban and rural areas. Operators prefer to cooperate mostly in Urban area due to difficulties of founding site locations and the high renting rates, then they prefer to cooperate in Rural areas to minimize the cost of delivering the service to overcome the low number of subscribers' problem.
- *Time of Cooperation* either in the beginning of network building or at as the network matures.

Old operators prefer to cooperate as the network mature and less willing to cooperate at the beginning of building network, while new operators prefers to cooperate in beginning of network building in order to reach areas reached by others faster.

- *With whom cooperates* either competitor, new entrant to the market or other, all current operators are not willing to cooperate with new entrants, 50% of the answers prefer to cooperate with other competitors because they trust their knowledge and experience. All are willing to cooperate with others such as electricity and gas utilities.
- *Level of cooperation* the researcher found that all operators are willing to cooperate in building sites (including towers) and then fiber optics and transmission systems.

Figure 5.8: Cooperation Decision making flow chart

Cooperation in building a 4G network

As a result of the dimensioning model designed to test the cooperation in building the 4G network with different cooperation scenarios we can conclude that cooperation will save company's CAPEX with percentages starts from 30 up to 52% and the biggest saving can be achieved by the smallest market sharer, this result explains why market leaders prefer not to cooperate in building 4G networks with smallest sharer because the smaller can fill the gap with them easily with lower cost. Also it explains the answers of question (15) in the interview where some operator's representatives interviewed refused the option of cooperation in this type of networks.

Figure 5.9: Zain Different Savings in building an LTE Network

Figure 5.10: MTN Different Savings in building an LTE Network

Figure 5.11: Sudani Different Savings in building an LTE Network

Another additional benefit that can be observed from the saving in building an LTE network jointly is the saving of the country's foreign exchange reserve because most of the network elements are usually imported from outside the country.

Table 5.34: Foreign Reserve Saving in building an LTE Network

No	Cooperation	Foreign reserve saving	
		Amount USD	Percentage
1	Each Company invests alone	\$0	0%
2	Zain alone (MTN Sudani Cooperate)	\$17,085,000	22%
3	MTN alone (Zain Sudani Cooperate)	\$17,085,000	22%
4	Sudani alone (MTN Zain Cooperate)	\$17,083,801	22%
5	All Companies invest together	\$34,170,000	45%

Figure 5.12: Foreign Reserve Saving in building an LTE Network

Environmental hazards

From the field study the environmental hazards from using generator sets in telecom sites due to exhaust emissions will be reduced minimum by 50%, although there is an addition load to the generator but still the fuel consumption the same because normally in areas where the main power supply is generator companies uses heavy duty set with high power and do not reach the minimum generation level. For the noise from generator set in some cases the researcher registered two sites with about 5 meters distance and each one has a separate generator, if we assume the two generators are with the same noise level , then cooperation will reduce the noise level by 3db.

Chapter six

Conclusions

Results Summary

This research reached several results regarding cooperation in strategy implementation in telecommunication infrastructure, these results gave answers to the research questions and explained the drivers of cooperation, the barriers that limits cooperation and the benefits of cooperation for companies. Main results are listed below.

Current cooperation level

Cooperation in Sites

The implemented cooperation level is too low compared to the existing built infrastructure, the highest cooperation degree is represented by Zain company, Zain cooperated in sites with operators (Sudatel) and many other enterprises with a total of 70 sites according to its data base by the end of 2013, these 70 sites represents 3.13% of the Zain's total sites, MTN has implemented site cooperation by collocating around 10 sites with SETCO, these 10 sites represents 0.5% of MTN's total sites, Sudatel cooperation data are not available.

Cooperation in fiber cable laying

The real cooperation in fiber is better than the site cooperation level, the cooperation is in about 12% of the 18629 kilometers of fiber already laid in the country, the cooperation is represented by the two agreement Zain- Canar and MTN-SETCO with a total length of 2210 kilometers.

these cooperation has resulted in CAPEX saving for the cooperated companies equals to 35,580,000 USD.

CAPEX and OPEX Savings

Can get savings in different CAPEX items starting from 20%, and for OPEX the saving is starting from 25% .

Cooperation drivers

The drivers that may encourage cooperation are Cost reduction, new revenue stream, regulator policies, enhance network easier, ease of maintenance, reduce service cost, enhance competition, new services and better QoS, share the risk among more than one operator, reduce expansion time/fast deployment of new systems/ cover new areas easy, increase capacity in congested area, lack of sites and reduce environmental hazards.

Cooperation Barriers

Barriers and reasons that led to the low level of cooperation are long term loss of competition advantage, type of antenna, radiation hazard (Site owner), cooperation with competitor, coverage is a competitive advantage, high leasing prices, lack of regulation, future expansion, lack of trust, hosting contracts not allow additional equipment and mast design.

Cooperation Decision Making

Factors affect the decision making are area of cooperation, time of cooperation, the cooperator type and level of cooperation.

Decision is usually made by considering trade-off such as: cost against cooperation, costs against revenues, saving time against building own infrastructure, retail against whole sale, additional revenue source against helping competition to develop, costs against service differentiation, costs against dependent on other operators and by applying business models.

Cooperation Willingness

The research results showed that mobile operators are willing to cooperate only in sites and fiber roots and they have no incentives to use national roaming. This concept characterized by access for any user to any network challenges the traditional way that established operators competes and invest in marketing, customers and networks.

MVNOs and National Roaming

For MVNO's and national roaming the cooperation can be organized using long term agreements describing terms and conditions for usage, fees and sharing of costs. The mobile operator providing the network capacity can act independently when it comes to network strategy and investments. Other operators sharing networks will be less independent when it comes to decisions about networks strategy. The cooperated partners need to agree on networks investments.

Cooperation in building the 4th Generation Networks

CAPEX saving will be from 30 up to 52%.

The highest saving will be achieved by the smallest market share.

Conclusions

Mobile network operators are currently faced with a number of challenges at the market. Mobile broadband access services are adopted and the demand is increasing. The increasing traffic volumes require investments in order to increase the network capacity. This development leads to a large interest in network solutions that can offer high capacity and low cost.

As shown in this research results, operators are able to achieve better competitive advantage through wider coverage in faster and cheaper ways by adopting infrastructure sharing in their business strategies.

Operators in many countries started cooperation in building or sharing networks with competitors or outsource network deployment and operation to other companies, typically suppliers of network equipment. In these examples the mobile operators cooperate about the networks, the relations to end-users are the same as if the operator would operate the network on its own.

In Sudan, companies also started cooperation but, with low level and mostly with non-competitors, from the research results: operators are resisting cooperation and prefer building new sites and expansion rather than cooperating with competitors.

Answers of the research questions

In this part the researcher will use the research results to give answers to the research question.

The first research question was

“What is the effect of cooperation strategies on the market value of the partnering firms?”

Market value is the value of a company according to the stock market. Market value is calculated by multiplying a company's shares outstanding by its current market price. If Company XYZ has 1 million shares outstanding and each share trades for \$50, then the company's market value is \$50 million. Market value is most often the number analysts, newspapers and investors refer to when they mention the value of the business.⁽¹⁾

Cooperation leads to cost reduction for both network deployment and operation.

Cooperation has a big impact when new base station sites need to be deployed. As found in the result the CAPEX saving will be more than 30% and the OPEX saving will be more than 20%, these savings can be invested in building other sites or introducing new services that can attract new customers to use the partnering firm's network and hence lead to new revenue, by adding the new revenues will attract investors to invest in the company which leads to increase in the share value and the market value.

The Second and third research questions were:

“What is the effect of cooperation strategies on the Capital expenditure of firms (CAPEX)?”

¹ “The Market Value Versus Book Value | Investopedia,” <http://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/110613/market-value-versus-book-value.asp>. accessed April 25, 2015,

“What is the effect of cooperation strategies on the Operation expenditure of firms (OPEX)?”

The researcher found that cooperation will help saving in CAPEX and OPEX as follows:

CAPEX savings:

- Power and cooling systems from 20 to 40 percent
- Civil work (buildings and tower) from 30 to 60 percent
- Generator sets from 50 to 65 percent

OPEX savings:

- Site rent from 25 to 40 percent depending on the number of cooperating companies.
- Fuel cost from 45 to 60 percent depending on the number of cooperating companies, the addition equipment load will not lead to extra fuel use because generally telecom companies uses high duty generator set with high generation power.
- Guard fees from 40 to 60 percent.

The fourth research question was

“What is the effect of cooperation strategies on saving the country's foreign exchange reserves?”

Obviously, it is clear from the answers of questions 3 and 4 and from the real cooperation cases in fiber laying , these savings in CAPEX and OPEX will lead to the saving of the country's foreign exchange reserve because most of the network elements are usually imported from outside the country, also from the results of the LTE network calculation made using the game theory there was a need to extra foreign currency when the number of the cooperated parties decreases, the foreign reserve saving will be between 22% and 45%.

The fifth research question was

“What is the effect of cooperation strategies on saving time during network deployment?”

From the real cooperation cases the researcher found that cooperation will help reducing rollout time of infrastructure when operators uses another operator’s existing infrastructure or build the infrastructure jointly.

The sixth research question was

“Why telecom operators in Sudan do not apply cooperation strategies?”

The researcher found that operators are applying cooperation strategies but with low level and mainly with non-competitors as shown in the fiber root cases, the first case was between a mobile operator (MTN) and the electricity company (SETCO) and the second case was between a mobile operator (Zain) and a landline operator (Canar), only Zain and Sudatel had some cooperation in mobile sites and this was from the time where Sudatel was the main shareholder of Zain, the main reasons found were : companies do not prefer to cooperate with competitors, coverage is a competitive advantage, lack of trust , long term loss of competition advantage, type of antenna, radiation hazard (Site owner), high leasing prices, lack of regulation, future expansion, hosting contracts not allow additional equipment and mast design.

The seventh research question was

“What is the effect of cooperation strategies on environment?”

From the field study the environmental hazards from using generator sets in telecom sites such exhaust emissions and noise will be reduced minimum by 50%

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested by researcher depending on the research results

National Telecommunication Strategy

1. The National Telecommunication Strategy is recommended to be updated with realistic objectives, detailed plans and clear responsibilities.
2. Encouragement of cooperation is recommended to be stated in National Strategy.

Activation of regulator policies

Although the telecom regulator in Sudan (NTC) had developed many policies regarding cooperation issues like the infrastructure sharing policy and the Mobile Virtual Network Operator's policy, but really they are not effective or we can say NTC is still encouraging operators to apply cooperation, due to this situation it is recommended to continue encouraging operators for cooperation by:

1. Training, workshops and seminars to help operators understand the benefits of cooperation.
2. Maximize the operator's role by participating in the preparation and modification of policies.
3. Giving incentives to the operators applying cooperation.
4. Mandate cooperation in areas where it is difficult to find sites.
5. And at last giving penalties to operators that refuse cooperation without giving reasons of that

Also NTC should prevent duplication of infrastructure to minimize waste especially in rural areas and highways where cooperation is highly applicable.

Improving transparency and information sharing

Operators need to know what is available for sharing, NTC should mandate publication on websites the details of existing as well as future infrastructure installations available for sharing by other service providers, such as the availability of space in existing ducts, planned deployment and upgrading works

Licensing infrastructure companies

In order to avoid conflicts and cooperation resistance by operators the researcher recommends that the regulator could consider licensing or authorizing market players that only provide passive network elements, but do not compete for end-users, such as mobile tower companies, public utilities companies with rights of way access, and fibre backhaul providers and hence telecom operators only rent sites or lease fiber capacity from them and save their CAPEX to use it in offering better services.

To establish such cases current operators can sell their locations to the new companies or jointly can establish a joint venture company owned by all of them.

Tower Design

One of the factors or reasons that limits the cooperation especially in sites is tower and antenna design, operators sometimes use masts with lower height or with lower weight so it was not possible to handle more than one or two antenna sets, it is recommended to use in future masts or tower that designed to carry more than three antenna sets.

Antenna Type

Operators may use more than one technology in on site like GSM, CDMA and LTE and this leads to use more than antenna set in one site, where it possible to use antennas that can operate with different technologies at the same time, so it recommended to used such antennas to keep space in towers for future use.

Contract Type

Some contracts force operators to erect one antenna set in site, operators have to sign contracts with site owner that allow them to expand if needed.

LTE Networks

During the preparation of this study, the biggest mobile market share Zain announced its launching of the LTE network, this will cause the between Zain and other operators to be wider, the others have to start building their LTE

networks, so it recommended to encourage them to jointly build their network for faster and economical deployment.

New Entrants

For new entrant it is not recommended not issue licenses of building own infrastructure, only license for Mobile Virtual Network Operator should be issued.

Future Research

Future research can be conducted to investigate areas not covered in this research like the effect of cooperation in LTE networks on the operational cost and interconnection cost. Also cost benefit analysis can be conducted so as to quantitatively assess the gains and losses from cooperation.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Abbreviation List

3G	Third Generation
4G	Fourth Generation
AT&T	American Telephone and Telegraph
AuC	The authentication center
BSC	Base Station Controller
BSS	Base Station Subsystem
BTS	Base Station Transceiver
CAPEX	Capital expenditure
CDMA	Code Division Multiple Access
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
DEC	Digital Equipment Corporation
DSP	Digital signal processing
eNodeB	evolved Base Stations
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
E-UTRAN	Evolved UMTS Terrestrial Radio Access Network
GE	General Electric Company
G-MSC	Gateway MSC
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
HLR	The home location register
HSS	Home Subscriber Server (HSS)
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies

LCD	Liquid crystal display
LTE	Long Term Evolution technology
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MME	mobility management entity
MNC	Multi National Company
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MSC	Mobile Switching Centre
MT	Mobile Termination
NSS	Network Switching Subsystem
NTC	National Telecommunications Corporation
OADM	Optical add-drop multiplexer
OPEX	Operational expenditure
PCRF	Policy Control and Charging Rules Function
PDN	Packet Data Network
RAN	Radio Access Network
ROI	Return on investment
SAP	System Application Product
S-GW	serving gateway
SMES	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TE	Terminal Equipment
UE	User Equipment
UICC	Universal Integrated Circuit Card
UMTS	Universal Mobile Telecommunication Systems
VLR	The visitor location register

Appendix B: Interview question – operator

Interviewee Name :.....

Interviewee Position :.....

Educational Level :.....

Employer :.....

1. Does the company that you work for apply any cooperation strategies with others:

Yes ()

No ()

If yes which is the most commonly adopted cooperation?

i. Coopetition (e.g. infrastructure sharing) ()

ii. Strategic Alliance (e.g. joint construction) ()

2. If your answer for question (1) is yes, please explain what the most commonly adopted infrastructure sharing categories are and what types of alliances that were adopted.

i. _____

ii. _____

iii. _____

iv. _____

v. _____

vi. _____

vii. _____

viii. _____

3. Is your company willing to cooperate with other companies to jointly build infrastructure?

If your answer for question (3) is yes, with whom you are willing to cooperate with a :
Yes () No ()

i. Competitor ()

ii. New Entrant ()

iii. Both ()

iv. None ()

v. Other ()

And why?

4. Is your company willing to cooperate in swap fibre roots with other utilities?

And if yes with whom you are more willing to cooperate with a:

Yes ()

No ()

- i. Competitor ()
- ii. New Entrant ()
- iii. Both ()
- iv. None ()
- v. Other ()

And why?

If your company has implemented such cooperation please explain in details its benefits and disadvantages if any.

5. From your point of view, what are the main drivers for your company to provide (part of) its current and/or possible future infrastructure (Active and Passive) for sharing?

- i. _____
- ii. _____
- iii. _____
- iv. _____
- v. _____
- vi. _____
- vii. _____
- viii. _____

To whom are you more willing to provide infrastructure a:

- i. Competitor ()
- ii. New Entrant ()
- iii. Both ()
- iv. None ()
- v. Other ()

And why?

6. At which stage your company will be more willing to provide infrastructure for sharing:

- i. The beginning of the network deployment ()
- ii. As the network matures ()

9. What do you consider to be the main barriers for your company to cooperate in infrastructure (Active and Passive) with other utilities?

- i. _____
- ii. _____
- iii. _____
- iv. _____
- v. _____
- vi. _____
- vii. _____
- viii. _____

With whom are you less willing to provide infrastructure a:

- i. Competitor ()
- ii. New entrant ()
- iii. Both ()
- iv. None ()
- v. Other ()

And why?

10. When your company is less willing to provide your infrastructure for sharing?

- i. At the beginning of the network deployment ()
- ii. As the network matures ()
- iii. In both phases ()
- iv. None ()

13. What is the most important trade-off that determines your company's choices regarding to cooperation in sharing or jointly building infrastructure? From the identified trade-offs are both variables of equal importance or is any of them of higher importance and if yes which?

14. Up to which sharing category are you willing to cooperate in infrastructure?

15. For the 4th generation network, are you willing to jointly invest in building the network?

If yes with whom you are more willing to cooperate a:

Yes ()

No ()

- i. competitor with higher market share ()
- ii. competitor with lower market share ()
- iii. all competitors ()
- iv. none ()
- v. Other ()

And why?

16. Do you think that encouraging infrastructure sharing might help companies extend their networks further into rural and remote areas / hard to reach?

Yes ()

No ()

17. Do you agree that the ability to share other companies' infrastructure would reduce the costs of network expansion?

Yes ()

No ()

18. Do you agree that Cooperation with other utilities has helped your company in reducing the Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and operation Expenditure (OPEX),

Can you estimate the reduction percentage in for both?

Yes ()

No ()

CAPEX Reduction (Saving)	
OPEX Reduction (Saving)	

19. The Cooperation has helped your company improve on its service delivery through introduction of value added services(or introduction of innovative product) by means of using capital saved

Yes ()

No ()

20. Do you think that Cooperation in infrastructure sharing with other utilities will help your company in reducing the time needed to build or expand infrastructure?

Yes ()

No ()

21. Do you think that Cooperation in infrastructure sharing with other utilities will help your company in reducing the effect on environment?

Yes ()

No ()

Appendix C: Interview question – Others

Interviewee Name :.....

Interviewee Position :.....

Educational Level :.....

Employer : University () Regulator () Other ()

1. From your point of view, what do you consider to be the main drivers for a network operator to provide (part of) his current and/or possible future built infrastructure (Active and Passive) for sharing?

- ix. _____
- x. _____
- xi. _____
- xii. _____
- xiii. _____
- xiv. _____
- xv. _____
- xvi. _____

To whom do you think is a network operator more willing to provide infrastructure:

- i. Competitor ()
- ii. New Entrant ()
- iii. Both ()
- iv. None ()
- v. Other ()

and why?

2. When do you think is a network operator more willing to provide his infrastructure for sharing:

- i. At the beginning of the network deployment ()
- ii. As the network matures ()
- iii. In both phases ()
- iv. None ()
- v. Other ()

and why?

3. From your point of view , Where do you think operators are willing to cooperate in sharing or building infrastructure?

- v. Urban areas
- vi. Sub urban areas
- vii. Rural areas

and Why?

4. Do you think that operators will be willing to lease from infrastructure owners (non mobile operators)?

why?
Yes ()

No ()

5. From your point of view, what do you consider to be the main barriers for a network operator to provide (part of) his current and/or possible future built infrastructure (Active and Passive) for sharing?

- i. _____
- ii. _____
- iii. _____
- iv. _____
- v. _____
- vi. _____
- vii. _____
- viii. _____

To whom do you think is a network operator less willing to provide infrastructure:

- i. Competitor ()
- ii. New Entrant ()
- iii. Both ()
- iv. None ()
- v. Other ()

and why?

6. When do you think is a network operator less willing to provide his infrastructure for sharing: at the beginning of the network deployment, as the network matures, in both phases, in none phase or other

- i. At the beginning of the network deployment ()
- ii. As the network matures ()
- iii. In both phases ()
- iv. None ()
- v. Other ()

and why?

7. Do you think that infrastructure sharing will affect competition?

Yes ()

No ()

If yes , what are the precautions to be taken to avoid affecting competition?

8. How do you think is decision making done by a network operator concerning cooperation? Is the final choice for cooperation a matter of trade-offs or are there other considerations that drive his choices? Can you please explain?

9. Which do you think is the most important trade-off that determines a network operator's choices regarding cooperation? From the identified trade-offs are both variables of equal importance or is any of them of higher importance and if yes which?

10. Up to which sharing category do you think is a network operator willing to adopt-provide infrastructure?

11. Do you think that the ability to cooperate with other utilities would reduce the costs of network expansion?

Yes ()

No ()

12. Do you think that Cooperation with other utilities will help network operators in reducing the Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and operation Expenditure (OPEX)?

Yes ()

No ()

13. Do you think that encouraging infrastructure sharing might help companies extend their networks further into rural and remote areas / harder to reach?

Yes ()

No ()

14. Do you think that Cooperation in infrastructure sharing with other utilities will help network operator in reducing the time needed to build or expand infrastructure?

Yes ()

No ()

15. Do you think that Cooperation in infrastructure sharing with other utilities will help network operator in reducing the effect on environment?

Yes ()

No ()

Appendix D: Infrastructure Sharing Policy

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National Telecom. Corporation

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بري - شمال كبرى المنشية

Board of Directors

مجلس الإدارة

الموجهات التنظيمية للمشاركة في البنية التحتية للاتصالات

تمهيد:

- انطلاقاً من دور الهيئة القومية للاتصالات في ضمان وصول خدمات الاتصالات إلى جميع مناطق السودان بأسعار مقنونة عليها، وبنقائات حديثة مواكبة، وجودة وموثوقية عالية، ومن دورها في وضع سياسات وخطط وبرامج ونظم لتقديم خدمات الاتصالات وإنشائها على المستوى القومي مع مراعاة التنمية المتوازنة وخدمة الأهداف القومية والاجتماعية،
 - وبناء على دور الهيئة في تحقيق أفضل وأعلى كفاءة في استخدام البنية التحتية للاتصالات وتجهيزاتها في السودان،
 - وإدراكاً من الهيئة بأن المشاركة في البنية التحتية للاتصالات من السبل الفاعلة في تخفيض كلفة نشر شبكات وخدمات الاتصالات وفي حماية البيئة،
 - وإشارة إلى الورقة التشارورية التي عُمت لكافة المشغلين والاستجابة التي تسلمتها الهيئة من شركة زين،
 - واستناداً على سلطة الهيئة في إصدار الموجهات والأوامر واللوائح المستمدة من أمر تأسيس الهيئة القومية للاتصالات لسنة 2007م ومن قانون الاتصالات لسنة 2001م،
- تصدر الهيئة القومية للاتصالات الموجهات التنظيمية التالية للمشاركة في البنية التحتية للاتصالات في السودان و تسري على جميع المشغلين المرخص لهم وعلى كافة عناصر ومكونات البنية التحتية الخاضعة للمشاركة.

1. تفسير

ما لم يقتض السياق خلاف ذلك، تكون للمصطلحات والتعابير التالية المعاني المبينة أمام كل منها، وتكون المصطلحات والتعابير غير المذكورة هنا نفس المعاني الواردة في القانون واللوائح الصادرة بموجبه.

القانون	يقصد به قانون الاتصالات لسنة 2001م.
الهيئة	يقصد بها الهيئة القومية للاتصالات المنشأة بموجب أمر تأسيسها لسنة 2007م.
الاتصالات	يقصد بها إرسال واستقبال الإشارات أو الأصوات، أو الصور الثابتة والمتحركة أو البيانات بالوسائل المنخبة واللاسلكية ويشمل

ذلك نقانة المعلومات ووسائل البث الإذاعي المسموع والمرئي
والبريد.

يقصد بها وسائل الاتصالات التي تُستخدم في تطوير أو تصميم أو
تنفيذ أو دعم أو إدارة نظم المعلومات المرتكزة على الحواسيب.

يقصد بها منظومة الاتصالات التي تقدم خدمة عامة للجمهور،
يقصد به أي شخص مرخص له يقوم بتشغيل تجهيزات اتصالات
عامة أو خاصة.

يقصد بها المشاركة بين مشغلين أو أكثر في البنية التحتية
للإتصالات وتجهيزاتها.

يقصد به أي شخص مرخص له يمتلك البنية التحتية أو تجهيزاتها
أو يسيطر عليها.

يقصد به أي شخص مرخص له يقدم طلباً مكتوباً للمشاركة في
البنية التحتية أو التجهيزات التي يملكها أو يسيطر عليها مشغل
آخر.

نقانة المعلومات

شبكة الإتصالات العامة

المشغل

المشاركة في البنية التحتية

المشغل المالك

المشغل الطالب

2. أهداف ودواعي المشاركة في البنية التحتية

أهداف ودواعي المشاركة في البنية التحتية:

- (1-2) ترشيد وخفض النفقات الرأسمالية والتشغيلية (CAPEX & OPEX) للمشغلين.
- (2-2) تمكين المشغلين من التركيز على نشر شبكاتهم ونظمهم الأساسية بأقل تكلفة وأعلى كفاءة والتركيز على استخدام فارق التكلفة في تطوير خدمات الاتصالات الجديدة والخدمات ذات القيمة المضافة وفي تحسين مواقفهم التنافسية.
- (3-2) تخفيض كلفة نشر شبكات النطاق العريض بما يحقق سرعة نشرها والنفذ الميسر لها خاصة في المناطق الريفية والذاتية.
- (4-2) جلب فوائد كبرى للمشاركين بتوفير خدمات متطورة ذات جودة عالية وأسعار مقدور عليها خاصة في المناطق الريفية والذاتية تحقيقاً لمرامي الخدمة الشاملة والنفذ الشامل.
- (5-2) الحد من المخاوف والأضرار البيئية والصحية والاجتماعية التي قد تنجم من نشر شبكات الاتصالات السيلارية ومن تعدد وكثرة الأعمال المدنية المصاحبة لتمديد الشبكات وإقامة التجهيزات.
- (6-2) تشجيع نمو التطبيقات والخدمات الجديدة وترقية التنافس بالحد من حواجز الدخول للسوق خاصة في هذا العصر المتسم بالتطورات التقنية المضطربة والمتسارعة.
- (7-2) تحقيق أقصى وأفضل استخدام للموارد القائمة عبر تخفيض ازدواجيتها وعبر الاستغلال الأقصى لسعاتها وإمكاناتها.

(8-2) للتأكد من أن المزايا الاقتصادية التي توفرها المشاركة في البنية التحتية تسخر من أجل المنفعة العامة لجميع أصحاب المصلحة في الاتصالات السلكية واللاسلكية.

(9-2) تحقيق توازن بين الانفرادية (Exclusivity) في إنشاء البنية التحتية والنفذ المفتوح (Open Access).

3. أنواع المشاركة في البنية التحتية المتعارف عليها:

1-3: بالإضافة للمشاركة في مجال الربط البيني، يمكن تقسيم المشاركة في البنية التحتية المتعارف عليها إلى نوعين رئيسيين هما:

(أ) المشاركة في البنية التحتية غير النشطة (Passive Infrastructure sharing) والتي تشمل المشاركة في الأعمال المدنية وكافة العناصر والمكونات غير الالكترونية.

(ب) المشاركة في البنية التحتية النشطة (Active Infrastructure sharing) والتي تشمل المشاركة في العناصر والمكونات الالكترونية.

2-3: تشمل عناصر ومكونات المشاركة في البنية التحتية غير النشطة ما يلي:-

- (*) الأبراج والصواري (Towers & Masts)
- (*) الأنابيب (Ducts) والمسارات (Routes) والقنوات والخنادق (Trenches)
- (*) أجهزة الطاقة الكهربائية والبطاريات وأجهزة التكيف
- (*) نظم الإنذار ومكافحة الحرائق.
- (*) الكوابل بأنواعها.
- (*) الكابلات.
- (*) المواقع الطبيعية (Physical Sites) والأراضي.
- (*) المبانئ والأسطح والمأوى (Shelters).
- (*) غرف الأجهزة.
- (*) البنى التحتية للمرافق الأخرى (المياه، الكهرباء، و الصرف الصحي ... الخ)

3-3: تشمل عناصر ومكونات المشاركة في البنية التحتية النشطة ما يلي:-

- (*) الهوائيات وأنظمتها (Antennas & Antenna Systems)
- (*) وحدات نفاذ المشتركين للشبكة (e.g. BTS, Node-B, etc.)
- (*) وحدات التحكم في الشبكة الراديوية (e.g. RNC, BSC, etc.)
- (*) شبكة النفاذ الراديوي (RAN) التي تشمل الكوابل المغذية (Feeder cables) وأجهزة التراسل.

- (*) الشبكة الفقريّة (Backbone Network)
- (*) شبكة الترامل الحلقية (Transmission Ring Network)
- (*) نظم إدارة شبكة الألياف الضوئية (Fibre Optic Network Management system)
- (*) وصلات الربط بين الشبكات الفرعية والشبكة الأساسية (Backhaul)
- (*) الخطوط المحلية (Local Loop)
- (*) النفاذ إلى مسار البيانات (Bit stream Access)
- (*) الشبكة الأساسية (Core Network)
- (*) العناصر والمكونات الذكية بالشبكة
- (*) سجل بيانات الأجهزة (EIR) (Equipment Identity Register)

4. الأحكام والشروط العامة للمشاركة في البنية التحتية

- (1-4) يجب أن يلتزم المشغل المالك بمبادئ الحيطة، والشفافية، وعدم التمييز، والتنافس العادل، وعلى قاعدة (الأول في الأول) في مجال المشاركة في البنية التحتية.
- (2-4) يجب على المشغل المالك أن يدخل في تفاوض مباشر مع أي مشغل طالب للمشاركة في البنية التحتية وذلك وفق عرض مرجعي معد مسبقاً ومتاح يحتوى على المعلومات الكافية حول كافة المسائل المتعلقة بخدمة المشاركة المطلوبة. ويجب أن يبنى الاتفاق الذي يتوصل إليه على الكلفة الفعلية، وأن يستند في ذلك على آليات تسعير مناسبة.
- (3-4) يجب على كل مشغل مالك نشر معلومات مفصلة عن البنية التحتية المملوكة له القائمة والمخطط لها في المستقبل والمتاحة للمشاركة مع المشغلين الآخرين في موقعه على شبكة الانترنت وغيرها من الوسائط، وأن يقوم بتحديث المعلومات على أساس ربع سنوي على الأقل.
- (4-4) يجب على المشغلين مراجعة وتقييم اتفاقيات المشاركة في البنية التحتية القائمة لتتوافق مع هذه الموجهات التنظيمية، وتقديمها للهيئة خلال ستين (60) يوماً من تاريخ سريان هذه الموجهات التنظيمية.
- (5-4) يجوز للمشغل المالك الاحتفاظ بنسبة لا تزيد عن 25% من ساعات البنية التحتية المملوكة له كساعات احتياطية لأغراضه الخاصة.

5. إجراءات المشاركة في البنية التحتية

- (1-5) يجب أن يقدم المشغل الطالب طلباً خطياً مفصلاً برغبته في المشاركة في البنية التحتية إلى المشغل المالك بصورة لهيئة وعلى الطرفين الدخول في تفاوض مباشر للوصول للاتفاق اللازم في هذا الشأن.
- (2-5) يجب أن تجرى جميع مراحل التفاوض حول طلب المشاركة في البنية التحتية بتجرد وبالمصى درجات حسن النية. ويجب على المشغل المالك:
- (أ) عدم تعويق أو تأخير التفاوض.
- (ب) تقديم المعلومات ذات الصلة واللازمة لتحديد التجهيزات المطلوبة.

(ج) تعيين مندوب مفوض لعملية التفاوض.

(3-5) يجب على المشغل المالك الإجابة خطياً على طلب المشاركة خلال عشرين (20) يوم عمل من تاريخ استلام طلب المشاركة، سواء كانت الإجابة بالموافقة، أو بتقديم عرض بديل، أو برفض مصحوب بالأسباب والمبررات شريطة اعتمادها من الهيئة. وفي حالة عدم تلقي المشغل الطالب إجابة من المشغل المالك خلال هذه الفترة، يحق للمشغل الطالب إحالة الأمر إلى الهيئة لاتخاذ الإجراءات اللازمة.

(4-5) في حالة الرفض، يحق للمشغل الطالب الاستئناف لدى الهيئة خلال فترة لا تتجاوز سبعة (7) أيام عمل من تاريخ رفض الطلب. وتتخذ الهيئة قرارها خلال فترة لا تتجاوز عشرين (20) يوم عمل من تاريخ تقديم الاستئناف، ويكون قرارها نهائياً.

(5-5) في حالة قبول الطلب، يجب أن يبرم الطرفان (المشغل المالك و المشغل الطالب) خلال فترة ثلاثين (30) يوم عمل اتفاقاً مكتوباً يتضمن الأحكام والشروط الفنية والإدارية والمالية والقانونية والجدول الزمني لتنفيذ الاتفاق. ويجب أن يودع كل من الطرفين نسخة من الاتفاق لدى الهيئة خلال خمسة (5) أيام عمل من تاريخ التوقيع عليه.

(6-5) باستثناء ما تقتضيه حالات الطوارئ، لا يجوز لأي طرف استبدال أو تعديل أو إزالة التجهيزات للمشارك فيها إلا بعد (45) يوم عمل من إشعار الطرف الآخر. ويجوز للطرف الذي تم إشعاره أن يقدم التماساً للطرف الآخر ضد الإجراء المراد خلال خمسة عشر (15) يوم عمل من تاريخ استلام الإشعار. وعلى الطرف الآخر الرد على التماس خلال سبعة أيام عمل من استلامه.

(7-5) في حال وجود خلاف أو نزاع بين المشغلين، والفشل في تسويته أو فضه بطريقة ودية، يحق للطرف المتضرر إحالة الأمر إلى الهيئة لاتخاذ الإجراءات اللازمة. وتكون قرارات الهيئة في هذا الشأن نهائية وملزمة.

6. دور الهيئة

(1-6) تتولى الهيئة حل الخلافات استناداً على لائحة فض النزاعات المعمول بها استجابة لطلب أي من المشغلين. ويحق لها فرض أي ترتيبات للمشاركة في تجهيزات المشغلين بعد التشاور معهم.

(2-6) يكون قرار الهيئة نهائياً وتخطر به أطراف النزاع، ويتم نشره في موقع الهيئة على شبكة الانترنت وغير ذلك من الوسائل.

(3-6) للهيئة من وقت لآخر، الحق في اتخاذ ترتيبات لنشر وتوزيع المعلومات المناسبة ذات الصلة بمجال المشاركة في البنية التحتية.

(4-6) للهيئة استخدام سلطاتها وصلاحياتها لتوفير المزيد من فرص المشاركة في البنية التحتية شريطة ألا يؤدي ذلك لتضييق المنافسة أو الحد منها.

وتقوم الهيئة، على وجه الخصوص، باتخاذ الإجراءات التالية:

تشجيع إعادة تطوير التجهيزات القائمة القابلة للمشاركة في البنية التحتية لزيادة سعاتها وإمكاناتها.

تقديم النصح للسلطات المحلية والولاية لاعتماد برامج لتشجيع المشاركة في البنى التحتية.

دعم تطوير قدرات المشغلين في التعامل مع قضايا المشاركة في البنية التحتية بطريقة كفاءة ومثلى.

(5-6) يجوز للهيئة فرض المشاركة في البنية التحتية بعد التشاور مع الأطراف المعنية ، متى ما اقتضت المصلحة القومية ذلك.

أشهد بهذا أن مجلس إدارة الهيئة القومية للاتصالات قد أجاز في إجتماعه رقم (2) لسنة 2012م بتاريخ اليوم العشرون من شهر شعبان 1433هـ الموافق العاشر من شهر يوليو 2012م، الموجهات التنظيمية للمشاركة في البنية التحتية للاتصالات.

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أوافق

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